

PARITTA

A HISTORICAL AND RELIGIOUS STUDY OF
THE BUDDHIST CEREMONY FOR PEACE AND PROSPERITY
IN SRI LANKA

By

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Introduction

*PARITTA*¹ is a very popular Buddhist ceremony in Sri Lanka. It is not an exaggeration to say that hardly a day passes without this ceremony being performed in some form or other in almost every locality. Its widespread popularity seems to be due to the fact that it can be performed at any time, at any place for a variety of purposes, both secular and religious, with dignified simplicity or pompous grandeur as the occasion demands, by anyone who wishes to have it performed. In fact, the Sri Lanka Broadcasting Corporation starts its daily programme with the recitation of an abridged version of the *paritta* for fifteen minutes at dawn.

This ceremony centres on the recitation, usually by Buddhist monks, of extracts from the Pali Canon, collected in a text called the *Catubbhānavārapāli*, *Paritta* or in Sinhala *Piruvānāpotvahanse*. Its objective is to ward off danger, ensure protection and bless the sponsors. It is prevalent in other *Theravāda* Buddhist countries such as Burma and Thailand as well, but this work is confined to a study of the tradition preserved in Sri Lanka.

This ceremony has a history which can be traced through records scattered in Pali and Sinhala literature, to the dawn of the Christian era. It has enjoyed royal patronage since the 4th century A. D. The building of a permanent pavilion for the recitation of *paritta* by *Parākramabāhu* I in the 12th century is an important milestone in the course of its development. Evolving through so many centuries it has absorbed several features from contemporary folklore and Brahmanical ritual practices. From the simple beginnings traceable through the Pali commentaries, which are 5th century translations based on older source material, it has developed into a complex form with steadily increasing popularity, permeating all strata of society. Despite foreign domination, subversive missionary activities, and the resulting cultural changes which continued with increasing force and subtlety through the last four centuries, this Buddhist ceremony has survived with amazing endurance.

Broadly speaking, this present study can be divided into three main parts. The first part which extends up to chapter IV, deals with the meaning, content and historicity of the *paritta*. The second, comprising chapter V, gives a detailed description of the ceremony, and its main types, as prevalent in Sri Lanka today. The third part attempts to take a bird's eye view of the component parts of the ceremony from a historical perspective to answer the why and the wherefore of all the ritual appurtenances and features. It is proposed to study this ceremony mainly from the point of view of oriental scholarship, tracing its historical development to the present complex form, and examining the cultural import of the ritual apparatus used, the symbolism involved and the function it performs in society.

Meaning of the word Paritta

The Pali word *paritta* comes from the Sanskrit *pari*+√*trā* 'to protect,' and it means protection. The corresponding Skt. word is *paritrāṇa* (*pari*+*trā*+*ana*). The Pali has dropped the suffix. In current usage the word *paritta* has a three-fold connotation. It means (a), a *sutta* or Buddhist sermon, the recitation of which ensures protection (b), the non-canonical text comprising a collection of such *suttas* and (c), the ritual at which this collection is chanted.

1 Sinhala. Pirit.

The gradual semantic evolution of this word can be seen through canonical and commentarial literature. Its earliest simple usage is attested in a number of passages and, *Vaṭṭakajātaka*² can be cited as one such instance. Here the present participle *parittāyanta* is used in the literal sense of protecting (oneself, *attānaṃ*). *Mātāpitaromaṃ ekakaṃ pahāya attānaṃ parittāyantaṃ palātā*. Tr : 'Leaving me alone, my parents have fled to protect themselves.' In the *Samantapāsādikā*³ *paritta* is used to mean precautionary measures taken to stop a fire.⁴

Ritualistic connotations of *paritta* too are to be noticed as early as in the *Vinayapiṭaka*. *Bhikkhunīpācittiya*⁵ which prohibits nuns from practising *tiraçchānavijjā*, 'animal sciences,' excludes *paritta* from that category. Here the commentary⁶ explains *paritta* as follows :— *Parittan ti yakkhaparittanāgamaṇḍalādibhedanṃ sabbam pi vaṭṭati*, i.e. by *paritta* in this instance all categories of *paritta* such as *yakkhaparitta* and *nāgamaṇḍala*⁷ are understood as permissible. However, originally in the *Vinayapiṭaka* the word may have connoted Buddhist *sūtas* recommended for self-protection, or perhaps even non-Buddhist prophylactic incantations designated by that name. Whatever the case may be, *Vinaya* has looked upon them with favour, hence their exclusion from *tiraçchānavijjā*.

*Kāmanītajātaka*⁸ shows the possibility of the existence of non-Buddhist prophylactic incantations called *paritta*. According to this source, exorcists employ three methods of treating a patient possessed by a demon, viz. *balikamma*, sacrifice, *parittakarana*, performance of the *paritta*, and *osadha*, medicine. There is nothing specific in this passage to indicate that *paritta* means the Buddhist ritual.⁹ Nevertheless, such an interpretation cannot be completely ruled out, especially when one recalls the very great importance attached to the driving away of demons and malefic influences in the Buddhist ceremony of later times.

In *Moraḷātaka*¹⁰ the protective incantation comprising an adoration of the sun is called *brahmamanta*. The verse which immediately follows it, comprising an adoration of Buddhas is called *paritta*.¹¹ The *Jātaka* explains the word *paritta* here as 'protection' (*imaṃ parittanṃ imaṃ rakkaṃ*).¹² It becomes clear, therefore, from these verses that certain incantations which were prevalent in pre-Buddhist India were accepted by the Buddhists. The fact that this hymn

2 J., vol. I, p. 213.

3 Vin. A., vol. II, p. 478.

4 *Parittam pi kātuṃ vaṭṭati, tiṇakuṭikānaṃ samantā bhūmitacchanam parikkākhānaṃ vā yathā āgato aggi upādānaṃ alabhivā nibbāti*. Tr : One should take precautionary measures, such as clearing the ground or digging a trench right round the huts, so that the spreading fire will go out without finding any fuel.

5 Vin. vol., IV, p. 305.

6 Vin. A., vol. IV, p. 937.

Also referred to in Vbh. A., p. 410.

7 Most probably *yakkhaparitta* (protection from demons) means *Ātānāṭiya* and *nāgamaṇḍala* (protection from serpents) means *Khandhaparitta*.

8 J., vol. II, p. 215.

9 *Bhūtavajjā bhūtayakkhādihi amanussehi... gahitassa balikamma-parittakarana-osadha-paribhāvīrādihi tikicchaṃ karonti*.

10 J., vol. II, p. 33.

11 Both verses are taken over to the *Paritta* text as *Moraḷaparitta* (See next chapter).

12 J., vol. II, p. 34.

worshipping the sun was designated *brahmamanta*,¹³ (or the noble spell) is also indicative of this recognition. *Morajātaka* records that the peacock who chanted this spell, comprising both verses, morning and evening lived free from fear and danger for a couple of hundred years. Snares failed to trap him because of the power of this spell. But, at long last, one day he forgot to chant it as he was infatuated by the cry of a peahen, and on that fateful day he was trapped. Such was the efficacy of *paritta* !

Thus, from simple unsophisticated beginnings, the word *paritta* gradually developed through canonical and commentarial literature and acquired a ritualistic connotation. This fully developed ritualistic significance is explained in the following words :—

*Antarāyaṃ pariharantaṃ tāyatiṃ parittaṃ ; parito vā sabbūpaddavato tāyatiṃ parittaṃ ; mahātejavantatāya samantato sattānaṃ bhayaṃ upaddavaṃ upasaggaṃ ca tāyati rakkhatiṃ vā parittaṃ.*¹⁴

Tr : *Paritta* is so called because (a), it protects by warding off danger ; (b), it gives protection on all sides or from all calamities ; or (c), by the power of its great majesty it protects beings from fears, calamities and dangers arising from all quarters.

As warding off danger and assuring protection, peace and well-being are the main objectives, *paritta* can best be described as a prophylactic ceremony.

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Analysis of the Paritta Text

The *Paritta* text, called *Pirit-pota* in Sinhala, is an anthology of 29 *suttas* collected together from various parts of the Pali Canon. Its older name is *Catubhānavārapāli* (Cbp.) which means the text comprising four chapters. Cbp. proper comes to a close with the 22nd, i.e. *Āṭṭhāṅṅiyasutta*. The last seven *suttas* have been appended to it at a later date.

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The following table shows a list of the *parittas* together with the identification of their sources and a brief description of their contents :—

Suttas	Identification of source	Contents in brief
1. <i>Saraṅgamana</i>	.. Kh. I	.. Seeking refuge in Buddha, Dhamma and Saṅgha
2. <i>Dasa sikkhāpada</i>	.. Kh. II	.. The ten precepts
3. <i>Sāmaṇerapañha</i>	.. Kh. IV	.. Questionnaire at initiation of novices
4. <i>Dvattiṃsākāra</i>	.. Kh. III	.. Meditation on bodily impurities
5. <i>Paccavekkhanā</i>	.. A. vol. III, p. 388	.. Correct attitude of a monk towards requisites such as food, clothing etc.
6. <i>Dasadhammasutta</i>	.. A. vol. V, p. 87	.. Introspection for maintaining the spirit and purpose of renunciation
7. <i>Mahāmagalasutta</i>	.. Sn. p. 46	.. Lay ethics
8. <i>Ratanasutta</i>	.. Sn. vv. 222-238; Kh. VI	.. Invocation of blessings by the power of truth related to the infallible virtues of Buddha, Dhamma and Saṅgha

¹³ Though *brahma* and *mantra* both mean 'hymn', or 'song of praise' in Vedas, *brahma* in Pali is used in the sense of 'noble.'

¹⁴ This is traditionally quoted by Buddhist monks at *paritta* ceremonies. It is cited in the *Pāli-Sinhala Pirit Pota* p.i. However it has not been possible to trace any textual reference for this passage.

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9. <i>Karaniyamettasutta</i>	.. Sn. vv. 143-152; Kh. IX ..	Cultivation of benevolence (<i>mettā</i>)
10. <i>Khandhaparitta</i>	.. A. vol. II, p. 72; Vin. vol. II, p. 109	Cultivation of benevolence against snakebite
11. <i>Mettānisamsa</i>	.. A. vol. V, p. 342	.. Merit of benevolence
12. <i>Mittānisamsa</i>	.. J. vol. VI, p. 14	.. Merit of sun worship and/or friendship and loyalty
13. <i>Moraparitta</i>	.. J. vol. II, p. 33	.. Adoration to sun and Buddha, morning and evening, for self-protection
14. <i>Candaparitta</i>	.. S. vol. I, p. 50	.. Lunar eclipse— <i>Rāhu</i> releases moon on Buddha's command
15. <i>Suriyaparitta</i>	.. S. vol. I, p. 51	.. Solar eclipse— <i>Rāhu</i> releases sun on Buddha's command
16. <i>Dhajaggariparitta</i>	.. S. vol. I, p. 218	.. Allaying of fears by contemplating Buddha, Dhamma and Saṅgha
17. <i>Mahākassapathera-bojjhaṅga</i>	.. S. vol. V, p. 79	.. Recovery from illness through meditation on <i>bojjhaṅga</i>
18. <i>Mahāmoggallānatthera-bojjhaṅga</i>	S. vol. V, p. 80	.. do.
19. <i>Mahācundatthera-bojjhaṅga</i>	.. S. vol. V, p. 81	.. do.
20. <i>Girimāandasutta</i>	.. A. vol. V, p. 108	.. do.
21. <i>Isigilisutta</i>	.. M. vol. III, p. 68	.. Enumeration of <i>Paccekabuddhas</i>
22. <i>Ātānāṭṭiyasutta</i>	.. D. vol. III, p. 194	.. <i>Sutta</i> approved by Buddha on the recommendation of the four Guardian Deities for recitation by monks as a measure of protection against demons
23. <i>Dhammacakkappavattanasutta</i>	.. S. vol. V, p. 420	.. Buddha's First Sermon
24. <i>Mahāsamayasutta</i>	.. D. vol. III, p. 253	.. Celestial retinue of the Buddha
25. <i>Parābhavasutta</i>	.. Sn. p. 18	.. Gateways to degradation
26. <i>Ālavakasutta</i>	.. S. vol. I, p. 213; Sn. p. 31..	.. The conversion of a demon named <i>Ālavaka</i>
27. <i>Aggikabhāradvājasutta</i>	.. Sn. p. 21	.. Who is an outcast ?
28. <i>Kasibhāradvājasutta</i>	.. S. vol. I, p. 172; Sn. p. 12..	.. The conversion of a Brahmin
29. <i>Saccavibhaṅgasutta</i>	.. M. vol. III, p. 248	.. Detailed exposition of the Noble Truths

BHĀṆAVĀRA I—SUTTAS 1-16

Suttas 1-6 can be fittingly described as instructions specially intended for young novices. As a matter of fact suttas 1-9, with the exception of 5 and 6 also occur in the *Khuddakapāṭha* which is generally regarded as a manual for beginners. It may be that both texts *Paritta* and *Khuddakapāṭha* evolved simultaneously to meet growing demands of an expanding Buddhist community.

On the other hand, if *sutta* 3 can be ignored it would be possible to surmise that suttas 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6 were prefixed to the *Paritta* text as purificatory measures to be observed by monks prior to *paritta* recitation. On this basis these suttas may be called *parikamma* or preliminary duties, monks being expected to :

- (a) express faith in the Three Refuges (*sutta* 1) ;
- (b) observe the ten precepts (*sutta* 2) ;
- (c) meditate on the 32 aspects of bodily impurities (*sutta* 4) ;
- (d) cultivate a detached non-indulgent attitude towards their meagre requisites (*sutta* 5) ;
- (e) keep constant watch over all actions and modes of behaviour (*sutta* 6).

It is quite likely that these suttas were prefixed as purificatory measures or preliminary duties and that sutta 3 may have been simply added to it following the pattern of the *Khuddakapāṭha*.

Suttas 7-9

At present these form the category known as great *parittas* (Sinhala : *mahapirit*), and they are invariably recited in all *paritta* rituals. But, according to learned monks, tradition has earlier regarded *Ratana-*, *Karaṇīyametta-* and *Dhajagga-suttas* as *mahapirit*.¹ Suttas 8 and 9 appear to form the nucleus round which the whole idea of *paritta* pivots. This will be discussed in greater detail later (pp. 11-15). In the *Mahāvastu*² *Ratanasutta* is introduced as *svastyayanagāthā*.

Suttas 9-13

These five suttas seem to form a cognate whole as they pivot round the idea of *mitta*. The word *mettā* is an abstract form of the noun *mitta* 'friend'. *Karaṇīyamettasutta* deals with the practice of all-pervasive *mettā* with a deep sense of sincerity and humility to all sentient beings of all climes and times. *Khandhaparitta* recommends *mettā* towards snakes by forest-dwelling monks. The next sutta *Mittānisamsa* extols the merits of loyalty in friendship. Friendship is the average human relationship which comes closest to *mettā*, and it is the only relationship which is independent of any biological necessity or utilitarianism. Now the word *mitta*, 'friend' is an epithet of the sun god as well. He who radiates life-giving energy to all sentient beings without discrimination or expectation is a friend of all. Thus, while *Mittānisamsasutta* has the dual theme of friendship and sun worship, the succeeding sutta is unequivocally a noble spell, "*brahmamanta*" for the ritual of sun-worship. It appears that the three themes (a), the active cultivation of universal friendship (*mettā*) (b), loyalty in friendship (*mittānisamsa*) and (c), the ritual of sun worship roughly corresponds to the *jñānamārga*, *bhaktimārga* and *karmamārga* of the Hindu tradition.

Suttas 14-15

During an eclipse, it is believed that the sun or the moon, as the case may be, is swallowed by the mythical demon *Rāhu*. But, according to these *suttas*, *Rāhu* releases them when commanded by the Buddha to do so. It appears that a myth which was already current in Indian society has been here utilised to show the supremacy of the Buddha over the mighty sun-god, for the sutta reveals that when the god himself is in difficulty it is the Buddha who comes to his rescue.

Sutta 16

During the mythical war between gods and demons (*sura* and *asura*), the gods allayed their fears and gained courage by looking at the banners of their leaders—*Sakka*, *Pajāpati*, *Varuṇa* and *Isāna*. This sutta maintains that fears may or may not be allayed by the presence of these leaders as the leaders themselves are not free from fear. To overcome fears the monks meditating in solitude are advised to reflect on the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*.

According to the earlier tradition this sutta formed part of the *mahapiritā* together with the *Ratana* and *Karaṇīyametta-suttas*.³ But in present practice it is replaced by the *Mahāmaṅgalasutta*.

1 cp. DA., vol. III, p. 969.

2 vol. I, p. 290.

3 DA. vol. III, p. 969 mentions the three suttas as a special group.

BHĀNAVĀRA II—SUTTAS 17-21

Suttas 17-20 share a common theme. They all show how monks have overcome physical ailments by contemplating the seven *bojjhaṅgas*, i.e. factors or constituents of knowledge. They seem to have been included in the text to illustrate, with specific examples, instances where acute physical disabilities have been cured with the help of meditation.

Isigilisutta (No. 21) is a unique sutta in the *Paritta* text as it contains an enumeration of *Paccekabuddhas*, nowhere else mentioned in the text. According to *Catubhānavārāpāli Aṭṭhakathā* it was included in the text at this point because virtues of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha* were extolled in previous suttas.

BHĀNAVĀRA III AND IV—SUTTA 22

Both *bhānavāras* III and IV consist of only one sutta, i.e. *Āṭānāṭṭiya*. The first part of the sutta which contains a request made by the four Guardian Deities forms *bhānavāra* III. The latter half in which the Buddha conveys the deities' message to the monks forms *bhānavāra* VI.

According to this sutta the four Guardian Deities inform the Buddha that there are powerful malevolent *yakkhas* who are displeased with the Buddha and his disciples and that they can harass monks and lay followers. In order to ward off evil arising from them, the four Guardian Deities, with the consent of the twenty-eight *yakkha* leaders, request the Buddha to allow his disciples to recite this *Āṭānāṭṭiyasutta* as a measure of protection.

Cbp. A. states that *Āṭānāṭṭiya* contains the virtues and powers of seven *Sammāsambuddhas*. It is placed last in Cbp. so that its power is augmented by being in association with the *parittas* preceding it.

Suttas 23-29

This is a miscellaneous collection of suttas added to the Cbp. at a later date, and they are recited during over-night *paritta* ceremonies as *yugapirit* (lit. twin paritta).⁴ The *Dhammacakka pavattana sutta* and the *Mahāsamaya sutta* are more popular than the others in this group. The latter is specially mentioned as a favourite discourse of the deities and is recommended for inviting good fortune.⁵

According to traditional reckoning in Sri Lanka suttas 1-21 are called *set pirit*, i.e. *sant paritta* (benedictory *paritta*) ; suttas 23-29 are called *sūtra desanā* (recitation of discourses) ; and sutta 22 (i.e. the *Āṭānāṭṭiya*) is called *hamāra desanā* (concluding recitation)⁶.

There are a few more Pali compositions, both verse and prose, which do not belong to the *Paritta* text proper, but which form an integral part of the chanting in all *paritta* ceremonies. It seems fitting that a brief discussion of them should be included here. As they have been collected in an appendix to the *Pāli Sinhala Pirit Pota* compiled by the Ven. Kirivattuḍuḍu Prajñāsāra Thera, they are taken up for discussion in the order in which they appear in his edition,

⁴ See below p. 41.

⁵ DA. vol. II, p. 694.

⁶ Cbp. and its commentary called *Sāratthasamuccaya* end with the *Āṭānāṭṭiyasutta*.

⁷ pp. 294-304.

Vāsi Pirita—Rain Paritta

This is an invocation to produce rain. Though it is not possible to identify the original source of this sutta in its present form, it is quite clear that the composition is based on the episode of *Subhūtitthera*⁸ and *Macchajātaka*.⁹ This sutta is not popular at present, but it is known to have been recited at the conclusion of *paritta* ceremonies during periods of drought.

Ānavum Pirita—Invitation to Gods

This sutta comprises a request to the deities residing in all quarters of the world to —

- (a) come and listen to the words of the Buddha ;
- (b) accept the merit dedicated to them and protect the dispensation of the Buddha diligently ;
- (c) protect the world and the dispensation of the Buddha so that all beings may live happily in the company of their own friends and relatives ; and
- (d) ward off evil and ensure protection and prosperity.

After making this formal request the monks announce the commencement of the ceremony.

Mahājinapañjara—The Great Cage of the Conqueror

This is a very important sutta recited in all *paritta* rituals and it is of special interest to note that there is not a single sutta in the Pali Canon which bears any resemblance to it.

As the title itself indicates the sutta attempts to build a powerful cage for the believer with the Buddha stationed on the head, the doctrine (*Dhamma*) on the eyes, the *Saṅgha* on the chest, *Anuruddha* on the heart, *Sāriputta* on the right, *Koṇḍañña* behind, *Moggallāna* on the left etc. etc. Again a cage is made of the *parittas* themselves, *Ratanasutta* in front, *Mettasutta* on the right, *Dhajaggasutta* behind, *Aṅgulimālasutta* on the left, with *Khandha-*, *Mora-*, and *Āṭānāṭiya parittas* forming a canopy above and the rest making a wall all round. The exhortation is that once the believer is encased or surrounded by these powerful forces, no disease, danger or enemy should harm him, because he is protected by the majestic power of the Conqueror.

The sutta closes with the following benediction :—

“May all misfortune, bad omens, calamities, diseases, unfavourable planetary conjunctions, disgrace, dangers, fears and unlucky dreams be averted by the power of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*.”

The theme of this sutta is quite alien to canonical literature and it seems to have been influenced by Tantric literature. In Tantric forms of worship *nyāsa* is an important rite, and by it is meant the “imaginary placing of different objects (letters of the alphabet, sages, deities etc.) in different parts of the body with which they are identified.”¹⁰ According to the *Kulārṇava Tantra*, *nyāsa* is so called “because it places in the limbs the treasures acquired rightly—*nyāyopārjita*, because it protects all, *sarvarakṣākara*.¹¹

A poem by the name of *Jinapañjara* is claimed to have been composed by a famous Thai monk named *Buddhācariya* about 125 years ago, and it seems to be almost identical with our sutta.¹²

8 Thag. A. vol. I, p.25

9 J. vol. I, p. 332

10 Chakravarti, p. 80.

11 p. 124.

12 I thank Dr. Saksri Yamnadda of Chulalongkorn University, Bangkok, for this information.

Āṅgulimāla Pirita—Āṅgulimāla Paritta

This is a special sutta the recitation of which is intended to facilitate childbirth. It is taken from *Āṅgulimālasutta* of the *Majjhimanikāya*,¹³ and its efficacy is derived from the power of truth. According to the *Majjhimanikāya* the Elder *Āṅgulimālu* makes an asseveration of truth (*saccakiriyā*), on the advice of the Buddha, to ease the suffering of a woman who had been in labour for seven days.

Jaya Pirita—Victory Paritta

This is obviously a *paritta* composed at a much later date, but no information is available regarding its authorship. It is a prose composition, repetitive in character and abounding in alliteration. It ends with five metrical lines. The gist of the sutta comprises an invocation of blessings for prosperity, health and longevity by the power of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*. The sutta is lengthened by a detailed enumeration of the powers of the *Buddha* and the *Dhamma*. However, this is not a sutta which enjoys popularity at present.

Gini Pirita—Fire Paritta

This is a short *paritta* and its first half is apparently modelled on the pattern of magical formulae in *Mahāyāna* texts. It is impossible to give a coherent rendering of this *paritta*, and its alliterative magical character can be shown best by quoting it *verbatim*.

Jālo Mahājālo jālaṃ mahājālaṃ jālite mahājālite jālitaṃ mahājālitaṃ mukhe mukhe sampatte mukhaṃ mukhaṃ sampattaṃ suttaṃ gamiti suttaṃ gamiti migayīti migayīti diṭṭhālā dantalā maṅḍalā rokilā kārālā dubbalā ritti ritti litti litti kitti kitti citti citti vittī vittī mutti mutti vutti vutti dhāraṇī dhāraṇīti.

When this is compared with a couple of spells (*dhāraṇipada*) of a few *Bodhisattva Mahāsattvas* contained in the *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka*, the resemblance is so great that it leads to the conclusion that the latter has had a considerable influence in the composition of the *gini pirita*. It is interesting to note the *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka* view that *dhāraṇipadāni* are spells meant for defence and protection. It says, "by those talismanic words being pronounced out of compassion for creatures, the common weal of creatures is promoted; their guard, defence and protection is secured."¹⁴

Bodhisattva Mahāsattva Pradānasūtra's spell is as follows:—

*Jvale mahājvale, ukke mukke, aḍe aḍāvati, ṭṭye ṭṭyāvati, iṭṭini viṭṭini cīṭṭini, ṭṭīti ṭṭyāvati svāhā.*¹⁵

The latter half of *gini pirita* is quite simple and it consists of an invocation of blessings by the power of the Buddha, and by the infallible truth of the statement that the Buddha attained Enlightenment by vanquishing the five *Māras* and that he preached the Four Noble Truths thereafter.

Aṭavisi Pirita—Paritta of 28 (Buddhas)

In this poem the names of 28 Buddhas are enumerated from *Taṇhaṅkara* to *Gotama*. Blessings are invoked by the power of their truth, virtue, equanimity and compassion. The idea of 28 Buddhas is put forward by the *Buddhavamsa*.

¹³ M., vol. II, p. 97.

¹⁴ *Saddharmapuṇḍarīka*, p. 372.

¹⁵ *ibid.*

This is a very popular *paritta* recited invariably in all *paritta* performances.

Jayamaṅgalagāthā—A poem for Prosperity and Good Luck

This is a very popular poem recited at almost all festive occasions. Nearly all school children are taught this poem. At wedding ceremonies this poem is recited in melodious tones by a bevy of young girls generally below the age of 10 years, all dressed in white, and standing before the young couple. At assembly, in schools, stanzas from this poem are recited daily.

The poem consists of 9 stanzas. Each of the first 8 recounts a feat of Buddha's victory over a fierce, deceitful and stubborn opponent. A refrain runs through these 8 stanzas : " May you be prosperous and fortunate by the majesty of this victory." The last stanza declares that these 8 stanzas bring prosperity and good fortune. Whosoever recites them daily attains safety, happiness and release.

It is believed by some that this mediaeval poem was composed in Thailand.¹⁶

Mahājayamaṅgalagāthā—The Great Poem of Prosperity

This is by far the most important and popular poem in all *paritta* rituals. It consists of 16 stanzas which reiterate the invocation of blessings and the prevention of disasters by the power of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*.

Cūlajinapañjara—Lesser Cage of the Conqueror

According to the first part of the poem Buddhas are stationed in all directions, and blessings are invoked to dispel sorrow, disease and fear, and also dangers arising from demons, deities, kings, thieves, fire, ghosts, wild animals, etc.

In the second part of the poem a cage is made for the believer by placing the Buddha on the head, *Sāriputta* on the right, *Moggallāna* on the left, *Tipiṭaka* in front, *Ānanda* behind, *Arahants* in the four quarters and universal protectors (*lokapālā*) on all sides.

The third part of the poem comprises long continuous benedictions. The concluding stanza in the poem is customarily recited during the distribution of *paritta* water and thread at the conclusion of the ritual.¹⁷

Origin and Development of Paritta

The earliest occurrence of the word *paritta* is to be met with in the *Vinaya Cullavagga*¹ and the *Aṅguttaranikāya*.² A monk is said to have died of snake bite, and when the matter was reported, Buddha says that such an unfortunate incident would not have happened if the monk had practised *mettā*³ towards all snakes. He then enjoins that monks should practise *mettā* towards all clans of snakes and suffuse themselves with benevolent thoughts for the sake of self-protection (*atta-parittāya*).

Buddha's admonition to the monks advocated the active cultivation of *mettā*, the psychological power of which was capable of subduing even the most ferocious opponent. Its efficacy is well attested in a number of episodes in the Pali Canon. *Mettā* is one of the four

16 Wells, p. 291, fn. 1.

17 See below p. 34.

1 Vin., vol. II, p. 109.

2 A., vol. II, p. 72.

3 Skt. *maitri*, benevolence, compassion, loving kindness.

brahmavihāras, and Buddha has always extolled the virtue of practising it. In fact *Mettānisamsasutta* which meaningfully follows *Khandhaparitta* in the *Paritta* text enumerates eleven advantages of the practice of *mettā*. One of them is that a person practising *mettā* cannot be harmed by fire, poison or weapons. *Manorathapūraṇī*⁴ and *Visuddhimagga*⁵ cite instances where monks were protected by the power of *mettā* from these agents of destruction. *Uttarā upāsikā* could not be burnt by boiling oil, *Samyuttabhāṇaka Cūlasivatthera* was not affected by poison, and *Saṅkicca sāmaṇera* could not be wounded by a sword. Moreover *Visuddhimagga*⁶ records how a cow feeding its young calf with intense love was not harmed by a hunter's weapon because of the power of *mettā*. *Nālāgiri* the infuriated elephant was instantaneously tamed by the Buddha with this all-embracing *mettā*. Such is the power of this well developed mental phenomenon, and Buddhists firmly believe in its efficacy to ward off danger. Again, according to an episode in the *Papañcasūdanī*⁷ a monk who was listening to the *Ariyavaṃsasutta* was bitten by a poisonous snake. Although he was aware of it he continued listening with rapt attention and faith. The poison spread and the pain became intense. He then reflected on the unblemished purity of his virtuous conduct (*sīla*) from the time of higher ordination (*upasampadā*). Great satisfaction and delight (*pīti*) arose within him when he realised the spotless nature of his character. This healthy psychological change acted as an antidote and he was immediately cured. It is further reported that he developed one-pointedness of the mind (*cittakaggatā*) and attained Arahantship immediately. The *Kulāvakajātaka* is another very fine illustration of the prophylactic efficacy of the practice of virtue. According to this *Maghamāṇavaka (Bodhisatta)* and his friends could not be crushed by the king's elephant and the king inquired whether they possessed a charm which protected them. The *Bodhisatta* replied that they observed the five precepts, cultivated benevolence (*mettā*), gave alms and did social service and that these were the *mantra* and *paritta* which they possessed.⁸ No better illustration is needed of the concept that active cultivation of virtue is *paritta*.

Again reflection on the *Khandhaparitta* cogently suggests that the Buddha advised the active cultivation of *mettā*, in this case particularly towards all snakes, to make sure that forest dwelling monks were well protected from a danger to which they were constantly exposed. With the passage of time, however, the injunction itself came to be popularly regarded as a sort of *mantra* the mechanical repetition of which was believed to ensure protection.

Though the *Khandhaparitta* can be considered as the most ancient of the *parittas*, the *Karaṇīyamettasutta* has superseded the former in importance, because it enjoins the cultivation of boundless benevolence towards all beings.....human, celestial and animal, known and unknown, near and far, friendly and hostile, past, present and future without any restriction ; whereas the *Khandhaparitta* is concerned only with a particular species, i.e. reptiles. Therefore, the *Karaṇīyamettasutta* with its greater comprehensiveness forms part of the *mahapirita*, the recitation of which is indispensable for all *paritta* ceremonies.

4 A., vol. V, p. 83.

5 p. 13.

6 *ibid.*

7 MA., vol. I, p. 78.

8 J., vol. I, p. 200. *Bodhisatto avoca : Deva añño amhākam manto nāma natthi, amhe pana timsamattā janā paṇaṇi na hanāma, adinnam nādiyāma, micchā na carāma, musāvādaṇi na kathema, majjaṇi na pivāma, mettāṇi bhāvēma, dānaṇi dema, maggaṇi samaṇi karoma, pokkharāṇiyo khaṇāma, sōlaṇi kārema, ayam amhākam manto ca parittāṇi ca vaḍḍhiṇi cāti.*

While *mettā* forms half the core theme of *paritta*, *sacca* (truth) forms the other and complementary moiety. *Paritta* assumes that Truth, when solemnly declared with sincerity and purity, has the inherent power of bringing about desired benefits. This is not a new conception which originated in Buddhism, for long before the rise of Buddhism, Indian thought was well acquainted with the idea that Truth is the source and instrument of great power.

The heated hatchet does not burn the innocent for "the true-minded having covered his true self by truth grasps the heated hatchet—he is not burnt and he is delivered."⁹

"It is truth which makes the earth bear all beings, truth which makes the sun rise. It is through truth that winds blow and that waters flow."¹⁰

"On truth all the worlds rest and immortality depends on truth."¹¹

It may also be noted in passing that this idea has continued in Sanskrit epic literature as well. For instance *Damayanti* resorted to an asseveration of truth when faced with the dilemma of identifying her *Nala*.¹² *Sāvitrī* rescued *Satyavān* from *Yama* by the power of truth.¹³ Similarly *Sītā* had recourse to this means to demonstrate the purity of her virtue.¹⁴

Such are some of ancient Indian beliefs in Truth and its power. Buddhism accepts the belief that Truth has power and this conviction forms an essential basis of *paritta*.

Āṅgulimālasutta of the *Majjhimanikāya*¹⁵ furnishes one of the earliest instances in the Pali Canon where truth has been thus utilised. The *Arahant Āṅgulimāla* takes pity on a woman suffering the throes of labour pains, and avers : "Since my birth as a noble *Arahant* I have never intentionally deprived a being of life. May you be well sister and may you have an easy delivery by the power of this truth," and the woman is said to have gained immediate relief which enabled her to deliver her child safely.

Similarly in the *Macchajātaka*¹⁶ the *Bodhisatta* is deeply moved by the misery of his kinsmen during a severe drought and prays to *Pajjunna*, the god of rain. He declares that he has never eaten or killed a living creature, even though he has been born among those who feed on one another. By the power of this truth he implores *Pajjunna* to produce rain. It is said that his prayer was granted ; the rains poured down, thus putting an end to their misery. Nowadays this invocation to *Pajjunna* forms the Rain-paritta (*Sinh : vāsi pirita*) though it is not formally included in the *Paritta* text.

The *Ratanasutta* which, according to tradition, was recited to rescue *Vesālī* from the triple scourge of drought, famine and epidemic, also embodies the same theme. It enumerates the noble qualities of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha* as infallible truths and invokes blessings by their power.

9 Ch., Up. VI, 16.

10 *Nārada-smṛiti*, p. 93, v. 213.

11 *Sanatsujātīya*, p. 170.

12 Mbh., *Vanaparvan*, sec. LVII.

13 Mbh., *Vanaparvan*, sec. CCLXLVI.

14 *Rāmāyana*, Bk. VI, Cantos CXVIII-CXX.

15 M., vol. II, p. 97.

16 J. vol. I, p. 331.

Though not included in the *Paritta* text there are many episodes in Pali canonical and commentarial literature which centre round *saccakiriya* or the asseveration of truth. The *Kaṇhadīpāyanajātaka*¹⁷ records a snake-bite cure by an asseveration of truth. According to the *Sambulājātaka*¹⁸ *Sambulā* cures *Satthusena* of a skin disease by *saccakiriya*. Many more relevant episodes could be cited, but these will suffice.¹⁹

The *Angulimālasutta* records the plain and simple asseveration of truth without any accompanying ritual paraphernalia. But the *Suppārakajātaka* displays signs of the gradual growth of a ritual. During a storm, the ship in which the *Bodhisatta* was travelling, ran into grave peril. In order to avert the impending danger of being wrecked, the *Bodhisatta* purified himself with a bath of scented water, put on new clothes, and taking a vessel filled with water in both hands declared : " I do not recollect having intentionally deprived even a single living being of life ever since I reached the age when I was able to exercise the powers of discretion. By the power of this truth may the ship be safe." It is said that the ship escaped danger and sailed away safely.

In this way there began the gradual development of a rite around the idea of the asseveration of truth. The scented bath and fresh clothes belong to the orders of preliminary purificatory rites, while the bowl of water forms part and parcel of the ritual proper. The present *paritta* ritual has come a long way from these early beginnings as will be seen later on. However, the belief in the power of *mettā* and *sacca* forms the basic structure of the *paritta* ritual.

The *Vamsatthappakāsini*²⁰ (circa, 10th century A.D.) records that the Buddha protected the island of Lanka by reciting what is called *mahāparitta*, but no further information is available in this context to judge what comprised this great *paritta*. According to the present tradition of Sri Lanka the *Ratana*, *Mettā* and *Mahāmaṅgalasuttas* form a special group known as *mahāpirit*, which is recited invariably in all *paritta* ceremonies. Learned Buddhist monks assert that the *Ratana*, *Metta* and *Dhajagga* are the *suttas* which were earlier regarded as *mahāpirit* and this contention is further supported by a passage in the *Dīgha Aṭṭhakaiḥā*²¹ which records this triad as a special group to be recited prior to the *Ājānāṭiyasutta*. Though it is not possible to ascertain exactly when the replacement of *Dhajagga* by the *Mahāmaṅgala* took place, the *Baṇa pirit katikāvata*²² mentions the new triad for the first time.²³ However the change seems to reveal a significant social change, especially when it is remembered that rituals, in general, bear a definite relationship to social conditions and aspirations of the people concerned.

The *Dhajaggasutta* refers to a mythical war between the *suras* and *asuras*, where the *suras* are advised to look at the banners of their leaders to overcome cowardice and boost courage. The *sutta* then goes a step further to add that reflection on the virtues of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha* is a far more effective means of banishing fear. This triad is a never-failing source of inspiration to all, including the leaders themselves. The *Mahāmaṅgalasutta*, on the other hand, spells out a lofty code of ethics for the promotion of the Buddhist way of life.

17 J., vol. IV, p. 31.

18 J., vol. V, p. 88.

19 *Andabhūtājātaka* J. vol. I, p. 289 ; *Suppārakajātaka* J., vol. IV, p. 142 ; *Mugapakkhajātaka* J., vol. VI, p. 2, etc.

20 p. 81.

21 Vol. III, p. 969.

22 P.S.P.P., p. 274.

23 Perhaps, *Saraṇāṅkara Saṅgharāja*, the great reformer of the 18th century was responsible for this change

state
possibilities //

✓✓

Reflection on the constituent parts of the earlier *mahapirit* group shows that they pivot round the following important themes, namely religion (virtues of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha* in the *Ratanasutta*), interpersonal relations (all-embracing benevolence in *Mettasutta*) and political leadership (inspiration from leadership in *Dhajaggasutta*). It appears quite meaningful that a ceremony which purports to promote worldly prosperity, should repeatedly stress the importance of these three aspects which are so vital for social harmony and coherence. || *

The replacement of the *Dhajaggasutta* by the *Mahāmaṅgalasutta* seems to tell the tale of a changed social order. So long as Sri Lanka had her own rulers whose avowed duty it was to protect Buddhism and the Buddhist way of life, inspiration from political leadership was meaningful to the masses. Once Sri Lanka lost her sovereignty and became the subject of a foreign power, inspiration from political leadership lost its relevance. Under such circumstances it becomes much more meaningful that an effort be made to retain one's own cultural identity by the preservation of one's own cherished ideas and ideals. The need for this may have been felt with greater urgency because the alien domination was reinforced by purposeful efforts at religious conversion. Therefore, perhaps, the obsolete *Dhajagga* was dropped from the *mahapirit* group. Its place was taken by the *Mahāmaṅgalasutta* which emphasizes a code of social ethics of a very high moral order. To withstand the impact of a political and cultural revolution perpetrated by a great foreign power, the Buddhists may have tried to fortify themselves with moral strength hence the inclusion of the *Mahāmaṅgalasutta* in the group of *mahapirit*.

Historical Evidence for Prevalence of Paritta as a Ritual

The rudimentary beginnings of the *paritta* in *Khandhasutta*¹, and *Āṅgulimālasutta*², have already been noted. It is now proposed to tabulate the available data from Pali and Sinhala sources regarding the prevalence of *paritta* as a ritual, adhering as far as possible to the chronological order of these records. As some of these records contain both early and late material chronological details of each work need to be given due consideration.

Milindapañha (Circa, first century B. C.)³,

The *Milindapañha*⁴ mentions six *suttas*, namely, *Ratanasutta*, *Khandhaparitta*, *Moraparitta*, *Dhajaggaparitta*, *Āṭṭāṇṭiyaparitta* and *Āṅgulimālaparitta* as *parittas* approved by the Buddha. It also discusses the following problems which reveal that *paritta* had already started to make an impact on society as an effective means for ensuring peace and protection :

- (a) Can *paritta* avert death ?
- (b) How does *paritta* become effective ?
- (c) When is *paritta* effective and when is it not ?

From these points of popular interest which have come within the purview of the *Milindapañha*, it is reasonable to surmise that the *paritta* may have already become a healing ritual. Rational believers are puzzled over the relationship between *paritta* and *kamma*. Hence the query whether *paritta* can turn away death, and if so how. Those who were more sceptical have inquired after the mechanism of its operation. But it seems likely that those who had had it chanted and gained faith in its efficacy at times, wished to know under what circumstances it would be effective and under what it would not. The entire discussion, together with the traditional explanation given, shows that the *paritta* had already become a ritual performed at times of crisis. But it does not reveal any information regarding its organisation as a ritual.

Vinayavinicchaya (4-5th century A.D.)

The *Vinayavinicchaya* affords the information that *paritta* water and thread were supplied to devotees on request. The ritual lays down that the *paritta* thread should be moistened with *Paritta* water before it is handed over :

*Parittodakasuttāni vutte dethāti kenaci
jalaṃ hatthena cāletvā majjivā pana suttakaṃ
dātappaṃ bhikkhunā katvā tesāṃ eva ca santakaṃ
attano udakaṃ tesāṃ suttakaṃ vā deti dukkaṭaṃ*⁵.

According to tradition the author of the *Vinayavinicchaya* is a senior contemporary of *Buddhaghosa*. If the traditional view is accepted it follows that the *Vinayavinicchaya* is older than the Pali commentaries. This leads to the conclusion that the earliest references to *paritta* water and thread are found in the *Vinayavinicchaya*.

1 A., vol. II, p. 72 ; Vin., vol. II, p. 109.

2 M., vol. II, p. 97.

3 But the passage relevant to the discussion may be at least a couple of centuries later.

4 p. 150.

5 vv. 491-492. Tr. If someone makes a request for *paritta* water and thread, the monk should stir the water with his hand, moisten the thread and hand over (lit. giving them full possession). It is wrong, however, to give away one's own (i.e. a monk's) water and thread. (Whoever wishes to get *Paritta* protection should provide water and thread).

main
975 1924
earlier

Pali Commentaries (5th century A.D.)

Paramatthajotikā—the Commentary on Khuddakapāṭha⁶

The commentary on *Ratanasutta* gives the following account regarding its origin. In order to save the great city of *Vesāli* from famine, plague and demoniac influences the Buddha caused Ānanda to recite *Ratanasutta* along the streets of the city and sprinkle water from the Buddha's alms bowl. No sooner did the demons come in contact with this water than they fled and the epidemic subsided. The people then constructed an assembly hall in the city, anointed it with all perfumes, tied a canopy above, decorated it in various ways and prepared a seat for the Buddha. After the Buddha sat himself on this seat, the monks, members of the royalty and the common subjects occupied appropriate seats. *Sakka*, king of the gods, arrived, accompanied by his celestial retinue. *Ānanda* also joined this congregation, together with the city folk, after making the city safe and secure by reciting *Ratanasutta*. Then the Buddha preached the same *sutta* to this entire assembly, and He repeated it for seven consecutive days. He further recommended the recitation of *paritta* to avert similar calamities in the future, making use of ritual paraphernalia employed in folk rituals.

This episode is traditionally recounted as the first *paritta* ritual. The important ritualistic features observable here are the ritual water, the decorated hall provided with a canopy, and chanting continued for seven days.

Dhammapadaṭṭhakathā—Commentary on Dhammapada

Dighāyukumāravatthu of the *Dhammapada* commentary⁷ provides further evidence regarding the development of the *paritta* ritual. In this episode, the Buddha demonstrates a ritualistic device to avert the untimely death of a Brahmin's child. The Buddha advised the Brahmin to construct a *maṇḍapa* (pavilion) at the entrance to his house, set up a small seat (*piṭṭhikā*) in the centre, arrange eight or sixteen seats around it and cause the Buddhist monks to occupy them and chant *paritta* for seven days continuously. After all preparations had been made in accordance with the Buddha's instructions, the child was placed on the centre seat and the monks sat round him and chanted *paritta* for seven days and seven nights without interruption. On the seventh night the Buddha too joined the recitation. The demon *Avaruddhaka* who had come to seize the child found no opportunity, as the mighty Gods too had flocked round the Buddha and his disciples who were reciting *paritta*, and he went away disappointed. Thus the child was saved and he enjoyed longevity and was named *Āyuvaḍḍhanakumāra*.

The construction of a special *maṇḍapa* or pavilion with seats for the monks inside it chanting *paritta* for seven days and nights continuously, while the child who needed protection remained inside the *maṇḍapa* occupying a central seat—these are certainly advanced ritual features not found in the *Vesāli* episode.

Sumaṅgalavilāsini—Commentary on Dighanikāya

The commentary on *Āṭṭhānāṭṭiyasutta*⁸ gives a graphic description of the *paritta* as a ritual. In view of its importance, and in order to give a complete picture, a free translation of the passage is given below :

“ These are the preliminaries (*parikamma*) for the *paritta* : *Āṭṭhānāṭṭiya* should not be recited first. For seven days the *Metta*, *Dhajagga* and *Ratana suttas* should be recited. Thereafter if (the demon) releases (the patient) it is well and good. if

6 Kh. A., p. 164.

7 Dh. A., vol. II, pp. 235-239.

8 DA., vol. III, p. 969.

he does not, the *Āṭānāṭiya* should be chanted. A monk reciting the *Āṭānāṭiya* should not partake of pastries or meat,⁹ and he should not live in the cemetery, for the demons (*amanussā*, lit. non-humans) may get a chance (to harm). The site of the ritual should be purified by anointing it with fresh cowdung. A clean seat must be prepared for the monk to sit on.¹⁰ When the monk is led out from the temple for reciting the *paritta*, he should be surrounded by men armed with shields and weapons. *Paritta* should not be recited in the open air. It should be recited with the doors and windows closed, surrounded by armed men.¹¹ The monk reciting the *paritta* must have his mind filled with *mettā*.¹² First the laymen should be made to repeat the five precepts after the monk and then *paritta* should be recited. If the patient is not released even by these methods he should be made to lie on the *cetiya* (pagoda) premises. There an offering of a seat must be made (*āsanapūjaṃ kāretvā*) oil lamps should be lit and the *cetiya* premises should be swept. Then *Maṅgalasutta* should be recited. An assembly of all monks¹³ must be summoned (The demon should then be addressed thus). 'There is an old tree in the temple premises. The community of monks expects your arrival there.' The demon will be obliged to attend the assembly.¹⁴ Then the patient who is possessed by the demon should be questioned : 'What is your name ?' When the name (of the demon) is announced he should be addressed by name : 'So-and-so, the merit resulting from the offerings of incense, garlands, seat and alms belong to you. *Mahāmaṅgalagāthā* have been recited by the monks to please you. Through respect for the monks you should release the patient.' If the demon still does not release the patient, the gods¹⁵ should be informed as follows : 'Do you know this demon does not obey us. We therefore, carry out the Buddha's orders.' So saying *paritta* should be recited. These are the preliminaries for laymen.

If it happens to be a monk who is possessed by a demon, seats should be washed and an assembly of all monks should be summoned. Merit of the offerings of incense, garlands, etc., should be dedicated to the demon and the *paritta* should be recited. These are the preliminaries for monks."

This passage shows a marked development of the *paritta* as a ritual from the earlier accounts of *Vesāli* and *Dīghāyukumāra*. The idea of preliminary rites is fully accepted. *Paritta* lasting for seven days is known. The *Āṭānāṭiya* is recommended for recitation as a last resort. The germinal stage of the present day *dēvadūtayā* (messenger to the gods) and *doorakaḍa asna* (sermon at the threshold) is also seen in the message sent to the *amanussa* (demons, lit. non-humans) and *devatās* (deities). Articles of worship such as incense, garlands and oil lamps have been utilised. It is also obvious that *paritta* is beginning to replace occult practices.

9 DAT., vol. III, p. 208 : Fish, ghee and fried cakes too should be avoided.

10 *ibid.* Personal cleanliness of the monk is also desired.

11 *ibid.* This forms external protection.

12 *ibid.* This forms internal protection.

13 *ibid.* p. 209. Living in the temple or in the village.

14 *ibid.* Through fear of Buddha's command and kings' command.

15 *ibid.* *yakkhasenāpatnam.*

Chronicles

Mahāvamsa (6th century A.D.)

The *Mahāvamsa* which ends with the reign of *Mahāsena* does not refer to any *paritta* ritual conducted by a king. However, in the episode of the first colonisation of Lanka by *Vijaya*, it is said that the god *Uppalavanna*, on the instructions of *Sakka*, protected *Vijaya* and his followers with *paritta* thread by the power of which the *yakṣas* were unable to harm them.¹⁶ This is undoubtedly an anachronism appended to the legend of *Vijaya* after the *paritta* had gained popularity as a prophylactic ritual. It is noteworthy that the *Dīpavamsa* makes no mention of *paritta* in this context.

During the enshrining of relics in the Great *Stūpa* by *Duṭṭhagāmaṇī* monks are said to have recited the *dhamma* in chorus. This was called *gaṇasajjhāyanā*.¹⁷ If the *paritta* had been known at that time, it was a most fitting occasion to have had it recited. Therefore, it is reasonable to surmise that *paritta* was not in vogue at the time of *Duṭṭhagāmaṇī*'s reign. However, *gaṇasajjhāyanā* or recital of the *dhamma* in unison by the monks was performed on auspicious occasions.¹⁸

Cūlavamsa

The first recorded instance of a *paritta* ritual conducted by a king occurs in the *Cūlavamsa*.¹⁹ King *Upatissa I* caused it to be performed when the country was vexed by a famine and plague during the 4th century A.D. The king came to know for the first time about the recitation of the *Ratanasutta* by *Ananda* in the rescue of *Vesāli*, and resolved to perform a similar ritual. An image of the Buddha was fashioned out of gold, with a stone alms bowl filled with water placed on the palms. This was mounted on a chariot and taken round the city streets. The king and his subjects observed *uposatha* vows. The king went along the streets of the city accompanied by the monks reciting *Ratanasutta* and sprinkling water from the Buddha's alms bowl. It is reported that heavy rains came after the ritual, and that the famine and plague subsided. The king also decreed that this ritual be performed during calamities of his nature.

Aggabodhi IV (626-641 A.D.) is said to have had the *paritta* recited several times.²⁰

By the reign of *Sena II* (851-885) the *Ratanasutta* had gained such prominence that he had it inscribed on a gold plate and celebrated the occasion with a great festival. He caused the *Abhidhamma* too to be recited. Then he safeguarded his subjects against the danger of plague by having *paritta* recited and *paritta* water sprinkled.²¹

In the 10th century *Kassapa V* (913-923) also had a *paritta* ritual performed by the three fraternities in order to save his subjects from the perils of famine and plague.²² It is also recorded that *Kassapa* recited the *Abhidhamma* with the grace of a Buddha, sitting in a *maṇḍapa* adorned with jewels, and surrounded by monks.²³

16 Mv. ch. 7, vv. 9, 14.

17 Mv., ch. 31, v. 86.

18 But the *Thūpavamsaya* which is a much later work states that *piri* was chanted throughout the night after relics were enshrined in the Great *Stūpa*; this is obviously an anachronism. p. 200.

19 Cv., ch. 37, vv. 189-198.

20 Cv., ch. 46, v. 5.

21 Cv., ch. 51, vv. 79-81.

22 Cv., ch. 52, v. 80.

23 Cv., ch. 52, v. 49.

+ if we accept this evidence it dates the commentaries above to a later time.

Parākramabāhu I (1153–1186) is said to have built a permanent building called the *Pañcasattatimandira* for *paritta* ceremonies and distribution of *paritta* water and thread.²⁴

During the reign of *Parākramabāhu II* (1263–1271) a great heat wave had swept over Lanka with the threat of a severe famine. The king had several religious ceremonies performed in honour of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*, *ceṭiyas* and *bodhi* trees. In addition he caused a great community of monks to recite the *paritta* and bear the Tooth Relic round the city. It is recorded that the rains came down and averted the disaster.²⁵

Lastly, the *Cūlavamsa* records that *Kirtisīrī Rājasinḥa* (1747–1782) honoured Buddhist monks with the four requisites and had the *paritta* and other salutary texts recited by them.

Vamsatthappakāsini (1000–1250 A.D.)

The impact of *paritta* by the time of *Vamsatthappakāsini* had been so strong, that a *paritta* ritual has been anachronistically added on to the legend of the Buddha's visit to Lanka as well. According to this, after driving away the *yakkhas*, the Buddha recited the *mahāparitta* and tied a protective injunction.²⁶

Pālimuttakavinayavinicchaya (12th century)

This work²⁷ enjoins that monks should recite *paritta* for sick patients in an appropriate manner when requested by laymen. It emphasises that the thread should be moistened with water before being handed over. When exorcising a demon, a palm leaf (*tālapaṇṇa*) or a *paritta* thread should be tied on the hand or leg of the patient before reciting *paritta*. The text then repeats the same passage as found in the *Dīgha Aṭṭhakathā*²⁸ which describes the ritual practices associated with *paritta*.

Inscriptions

The *paritta* is also mentioned in some of the inscriptions of Sri Lanka. The slab inscription of *Kassapa V* (Circa A.D. 929–939) lays down that only those who are familiar with the *Catubhāṇavārapāli* should be admitted to the order.²⁹ This is the first instance when such a condition had been laid down as a pre-requisite for ordination. The Tablets of *Mahinda IV* at *Mihintale* (Circa A.D. 975–991 or 997–1013)³⁰ enjoin that monks should recite and practise *met pirit* (Pali *metta paritta*) before partaking of their morning meal.³¹ The Rock Inscription of *Parākramabāhu I* (Circa 1153–1186) declares that monks and novices are not permitted to enter the village at unusual hours except for some special purpose. A journey to recite *paritta* at an appointed place is exempted from this rule.³² An inscription of *Nissāṅkamalla* (1187–1196)

24 Cv., ch. 73, v. 73.

25 Cv., ch. 87, vv. 1–10.

26 *Vamsatthappakāsini* pp. 81, 95. *dīpavarassa rakḥhanatthāya parittam katvā āṇaṇṇi bandhītvā . . .*

27 pp. 11–12.

28 DA., vol. III, p. 969.

29 EZ., vol. I, p. 55.

30 EZ., vol. I, p. 78.

31 EZ., vol. I, p. 99.

32 EZ., vol. II, p. 278.

A.D.), on one of the columns of the *Nissankalatāmaṇḍapa*, establishes beyond doubt that this *maṇḍapa* was used for the purpose of chanting *paritta*. The inscription which was partially read in 1903³³ was subsequently fully deciphered in 1915.³⁴ It runs as follows :

“ *maitrīn lōka śāsana sanahā lōka vāsīṇṭa puṇyakṣetra koṭa āyatana
niśśaṅka latā maṇḍapaye hiṇḍū pirit (asana kuḍa) mā* ”

Tr. This (is the pavilion for the hearing of) *pirit* what time (His Majesty), seated in the Sanctuary, the “ Nissanka Flower-trial Hall,” provides in loving-kindness a field of merit for the peace of the world-dwellers and the Buddhist faith.

It is clear from this inscription that the royal sponsor was himself present within the *maṇḍapa*. This had been a custom prevalent in the 5th century too, for, Prince *Dīghāyu* is said to have been placed in the centre of the *maṇḍapa* on Buddha's instructions, when *paritta* was recited to give him long life.³⁵

Though meagre this inscriptional evidence is very valuable as it reveals the impact that the *paritta* had made on royalty. By convention, the *paritta* had been welded into the routine of the daily life of the monks and novices. It had also forged a very strong bond between the Buddhist clergy and the laity, to the extent that it had even caused the relaxation of some general and stringent monastic rules.

Sinhala Literature

The classical Sinhala literature provides ample evidence of the popularity of *paritta* as a ritual.³⁶ As the material is too copious only those data which mark a further development from ideas gathered through Pali sources will be discussed here.

The *Prayogaratnāvalī* which is a medical treatise compiled by *Mayurapāda*, the author of *Pūjāvāliya*, during the reign of *Parākramabāhu II* (1236–1271), prescribes the recitation of *paritta* for infant diseases. It was believed that various demons afflict infants at different stages of their growth during the first year. These demons should be appeased with appropriate offerings. Then the infant should be held over medicinal incense for a few minutes (*osu dum dī*) and finally he should be bathed after *pirit* has been chanted (*pirit karavā nāvamī*). The chanting of what is called *bālagrahadosa pirit*, i.e. *paritta* which is intended to ward off the evil influences of bad planetary combinations on children, is repeatedly recommended.³⁷ The *Vaidyacintāmaṇī* which is a medical treatise written by a Tamil specialist during the 15th century also prescribes the chanting of *pirit* for infant ailments. It also recommends *pirit* for *yakṣa-preta-roga-cikitsā*, i.e. for curing of diseases caused by demons and ghosts.

The *Daḷadā Siritā* which is a Sinhala work based on *Dāṭhāvamsa* composed by *Devrad Dampasaṅgināvan* (king's minister of justice ?) in the reign of *Parākramabāhu IV* during the 14th century, recommends as follows : “ When kings go into occupation of a new palace, the Tooth

33 *Archaeological Survey of Ceylon, Annual Reports, 1903*, pp. 18–20.

34 *Archaeological Survey of Ceylon, 1911–1912, Ceylon Sessional Papers 1915*, p. 100.

35 Dh. A., vol. II, pp. 235–239.

36 *Pūjāvāliya* (13th cen.), pp. 63, 64, 442 ; *Sinhala Bodhivamsaya* (14th cen.), p. 213 ; *Daḷada Siritā* (14th cen.), pp. 50–51 ; *Saṅga Saraṇa* (13th cen.), p. 8 ; *Thūpavamsaya* (13th cen.), p. 200 ; etc., etc.

37 *Prayogaratnāvalī*, pp. 20–25.

Relic and the Bowl Relic should be taken in first along with the *Saṅgha* who will recite *paritta* sprinkle *pirit pān* (*paritta* water) to protect the place before it is occupied.³⁸ Again, it recommends that the Tooth Relic should be taken in procession along the streets of the city in a beautifully decorated chariot drawn by an auspicious elephant, with virtuous monks chanting *paritta*, holding the *pirit huya* (*paritta* thread) and sprinkling *pirit pān* from a silver vessel.³⁹

Paritta is also chanted during the preparation of medicinal oils, most probably to heighten their curative effect. The *Snēha Śatakaya*, also called *Behet Tel Pota*, attributed to the 18th-19th century, recommends the recitation of *paritta* during the preparation of *divyāṅganādi tailaya* with *paritta* thread tied all round.⁴⁰ According to the *Auṣadha Muktaḥaraya*, during the preparation of *henarāja tailaya* too, *paritta* should be chanted and *paritta* thread should be drawn all round.⁴¹

Conclusions

A survey of the above material from original sources shows that the *paritta* may have become a ritual prevalent among laymen, perhaps on a small scale, during the early centuries of the Christian era. Hence the critical and rational queries raised in the *Milindapañha*. It was recognised by royalty as a prophylactic ritual for public welfare for the first time during the 4th century A.D. (*Upatissa I*). The erection of a temporary *maṇḍapa* for this ritual was known by the 5th century A.D.⁴² The employment of ritual accessories such as water, incense, garlands and thread, and the observance of preliminary purificatory rites, were also known by the 5th century A.D.⁴³ The construction of a permanent building for recitation of the *paritta* by King *Parākramabāhu II* shows that the ritual had become an integral part of the life of Sinhala Buddhists by the 12th century A.D. Its usefulness in paediatrics and in the preparation of medicines, shows that the chanting of *paritta* was beginning to replace Brahmanical occult practices, and to grow in importance as a multi-purpose ritual exercising great influence on the lives of an unsophisticated people.

38 *Daḷadā Sīrita*, p. 50. *Rajadaruvan māligā praveśa vana kala paḷamva daḷadā pūtra dhātuvahansē vaḍḍe mahasaṅgana lavā pirit karavā piritpān isvā arak kara tunuruvanāṣa pūja kara pravēśa vanuva isā.*

39 *ibid.*

40 p. 17, v. 137.

*pirit puravā nūl vaḷa āda vedahu laṅga iṅda nolasinē
mal bulat ran paṇḍuru sadamin uturu diḡa puḷa karaminē*

41 p. 9, v. 66.

*viyan bhānda uḷa suddha vilasin pirit huya vaḷa adinnē
....
....
soḍḍin mantara pirit kiyamin behet tel sūla lipa tiyanṇē*

42 Dh. A., vol. II, p. 237.

43 Kh. A., p. 164 ; D A., vol. III, p. 969.

Paritta as practised in Sri Lanka Today

In this chapter an attempt is made to give a detailed description of *paritta* as it is practised in Lanka today. As this is a ceremony which can be performed with varying degrees of complexity three broad variants of the ceremony will be outlined which represents a fair cross section from the simplest to the most elaborate. The fourth set out below is only a substitute ceremony conducted by laymen :

- (1) Sessional *paritta* (Sinhala : *varupirita*) ;
- (2) All-night *paritta* (Sinhala : *tis pāyē pirita*) ;
- (3) Seven-day *paritta* (Sinhala : *hat davase/sati pirita*) ;
- (4) *Paritta* recited by laymen (Sinhala : *gihi pirita*).

The common factor which runs through all these various forms is the recitation of suttas from the *Paritta* text which have been already discussed (*See* pages 5-11). This is the indispensable feature in a *paritta* ceremony. Intelligent monks and laymen believe that *paritta* recited even by oneself, while reflecting on the meaning of the suttas, and conducting oneself according to the precepts of virtue is as effective as *paritta* recited with ceremonial Paraphernalia, if not more so. Elements of current folk magical practices are absorbed into the *paritta* ceremony as external embellishments to satisfy the anxiety of the masses, who hope for magic to work at times of disaster. The efficacy of *paritta* nevertheless does not depend on the accompanying ritual. It is the practice among devoted Buddhists to recite one of the suttas belonging to the *mahāparitta* group every day either individually or collectively together with members of the family, at evening meditation or at bed time.

1. Varu Pirita (Sessional Paritta)

This is generally conducted in three, five or seven sessions each lasting approximately one hour, there being two sessions each day morning and evening. The ceremony can start either with a morning session or with an evening session. Three-session ceremonies are quite common, and those lasting for five or seven sessions are less frequent. These are sometimes substitutes for all-night ceremonies which cannot be performed due to lack of personnel, time, and, most often, money.

Invitation

The layman wishing to have the ceremony performed goes to the monastery and invites the monks. Generally he takes with him a small gift to the monks according to his means, some tea, sugar, fruits, fruit cordial or some such appropriate item. Together with this he offers a sheaf of betel leaves to the chief monk, greets him respectfully kneeling at his feet and makes his intention known. If the layman's need is not very urgent the monk will fix a convenient date, but if the matter be urgent as in the case of a dying man, immediate arrangements are made.

Preparation

Preparation for the sessional *paritta* is quite simple. The verandah or the sitting room is swept clean, a few chairs, according to the number of monks invited, are placed in a row and covered with a clean white sheet. A small table is placed in front, also covered with a clean cloth. A small pot or jug of strained water, covered with a white kerchief is also placed on the table. A small coconut oil lamp, a tray of fresh flowers and a ball of white thread complete the essential ritual objects on the table. Water mixed with turmeric is lightly sprinkled all over the house to ensure ritual cleansing. If available a few grains of paddy roasted till it has popped (*pori* or *vilañda*), mustard seeds and rice are sprinkled on the table and around the place where the chairs are arranged.

At the entrance to the house a basin of water and a towel are placed for washing and wiping the feet of the monks on arrival. Some light refreshments such as orange juice, king coconut water or tea and betel leaves are kept handy in the house to serve the monks at the end of the ceremony.

Preparation being thus complete, an elderly male goes to fetch the monks from the temple ; the monks are conveyed in a car if one is available ; if not, the monks are conducted in a procession, on foot, or they come on their own at the appointed hour.

The Ceremony Begins

When the monks arrive a young male member of the household washes and dries their feet at the entrance. If there are two boys, one washes and the other dries, but this task is never performed by a female as it is improper for a monk to be touched by a female. As the monks enter and occupy the seats prepared for them, everybody present respectfully greets them.¹ Soon, two monks busy themselves converting the ball of white thread into a three strand skein by a special simple method ; this is then wrapped round a rolled up betel leaf. The loose end of the thread is then tied round the pot of water. The oil lamp is lit and incense is burnt. After these preliminaries are completed the ceremony begins.

All the members of the family sit down in front of the monks on mats spread out on the ground, the person for whose special benefit the ceremony is performed—a sick child or a pregnant woman—occupying the central position. All clasp their hands in salutation. One of the monks, generally the most senior, requests the devotees to recite the *namaskāraya*.² After this he administers *pansil*, (Pali, *pañcasīla*) i.e. he leads them in reciting the formulae confessing

1 The act is called *vañdinavā*—See Reynolds, pp. 24–25.

2 i.e. 'the salutation.' *Namo tassa Bhagavato Arahato Sammāsambuddhassa*. "I bow to the Blessed One, the Worthy One, the Fully Enlightened One" repeated thrice.

faith in the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha* thrice, and the 5 precepts.³ When this is completed the monks take hold of the three strand thread, now called *pirit nūla*, i.e. *paritta* thread,⁴ the end of which is already tied round the pot of water. The rolled up betel leaf round which the thread is wound is handed over to the devotees, who, one by one, unwind the thread and take hold of it with hands clasped in salutation. The thread is gradually unwrapped to reach everybody, and care is taken to see that it does not touch the ground, and that nobody treads or jumps over it. Thus, when all taking part in the ceremony are connected by this thread, the monks start reciting the *paritta suttas* in chorus. The suttas generally chosen for recitation are as follows :—

- (i) *Namaskāra*
- (ii) *Iti pi so Bhagavā*
Svākkhāto Bhagavatā dhammo
*Supaṭipanno Bhagavato sāvakasaṅgho*⁵
- (iii) *Mahāmaṅgalasutta*⁶
- (iv) *Mettasutta*
- (v) *Ratanasutta*
- (vi) *Mahājinapañjara*
- (vii) *Cūlajinapañjara*
- (viii) Benedictory refrains.

If the ceremony is performed for the benefit of a pregnant woman, the *Aṅgulimālasutta* is also recited.

At the end of the recitation the thread is rolled back and placed on the pot of water. The monks are served with hot tea or coffee, or fruit juice, and specially prepared chews of betel leaves. The devotees pay homage to them prior to departure.

³ *Buddhaṃ saraṇaṃ gacchāmi*

Dhammaṃ saraṇaṃ gacchāmi

Saṅghaṃ saraṇaṃ gacchāmi

Dutiyam pi Buddhaṃpe

Tatīyam pi Buddhaṃpe

Tr. I take refuge in the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*

For the second time I take

For the third time I take

pāṇātipātā veramaṇi sikkhāpadam samādiyāmi

adinnādānā

kāmesu micchācārā

musāvādā

surāmerayamajjapamādaṭṭhānā

Tr. I take upon myself the vows of abstaining from killing, stealing, illicit sex, falsehood, and all types of intoxicants.

⁴ *parittasuttaka* is mentioned in J. vol. I, pp. 396, 399.

⁵ D., vol. II, p. 93. Formulae extolling the virtues of *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*.

⁶ See above pp. 5-11 for this and following suttas.

The same procedure is repeated for all sessions, be they three, five or seven. At the concluding ceremony a few more formulae are added to the recitation, to dedicate merit to departed relatives, deities, demons, *nāgās* and all living beings. The deities and *nāgās* are further requested to protect the people and the dispensation of the Buddha.⁷

The loud choral recitation ceases and a reverent atmosphere of fresh hope and well-being pervades. Respectfully the chief devotee rolls back the thread and hands it over to the monks. The person for whom the ceremony is specially performed is then summoned near the monks. One monk pours *paritta* water into his or her cupped hands while all the monks recite the following formula in unison :—

*Bhavatu sabbamaṅgalaṃ
rakkhantu sabbadevatā
sabbabuddhānubhāvena/sabbadhammānubhāvena/sabbasaṅghānubhāvena
sadā sotthi bhavantu te
Icchitaṃ patthitaṃ tuyhaṃ
khippam eva samijjhatu
mā te bhavatvantarāyo
sukhī dīghāyuko bhava*

Tr. “ May yours be all good fortune. May all gods protect you. By the blessings of all Buddhas (*Dhamma* and *Sangha*) may you be well and happy. May all your wishes and aspirations come to fruition immediately. May you have no danger to encounter. May you be happy and may you live long.”

Reverentially the devotee receives the water, drinks some of it and puts the rest on his face and head. Generally the water is not wiped, it is left to dry on the skin.

After distributing the sacred *paritta* water to a few in this manner the monk takes a piece of *paritta* thread about a foot in length by breaking it with his hands. No implement is ever used to cut it. This is moistened with *paritta* water and then tied on the right wrist or arm of the devotee while reciting the following formula :

*Sabbe Buddhā balappattā
paccekānaṃ ca yaṇi balaṃ
arahantānaṃ ca tejena
rakkhaṃ bandhāmi sabbaso*

7 (a) *Idaṃ vo ñātinaṃ hotu
sukhitaṃ hontu ñātayo*

Tr. May this merit accrue to your relatives, may they be happy !

(b) *Ettāvatā ca amhehi
sambhatoṃ piṇḍasampadaṃ
sabbe devā|bhūtā|sattā anumodantu
sabbasampattisiddhiyā*

Tr. May all gods, non-human beings and creatures share in the merit we have thus accumulated and promote all blessings !

(c) *Ākāsaṭṭhā ca bhummaṭṭhā
devā nāgā mah'iddhikā
piṇḍaṃ taṃ anumoditvā
ciraṃ rakkhantu sāsanaṃ|desanaṃ|maṇi paraṃ*

Tr. May the gods and *nagas* of mighty powers residing in space and those inhabiting on earth, rejoice in this merit and may they protect for a long time the dispensation (of the Buddha), the teachings (of the Buddha), myself and all others !

Tr. " All Buddhas have attained great powers, and so have *Paccekabuddhas* and *Arahants*.
By the majesty of their powers I tie a protection valid in all respects."

Monks are permitted to tie the *paritta* thread only on males. In the case of females a layman ties it while the monks recite the formula.

After the distribution of *paritta* water and thread the monks are served hot tea or fruit juice and betel leaves and they depart. Neighbours who wish to have *paritta* water and thread are also welcome to receive them. If there is water remaining, it is disposed of the following day or the day after, generally in a place where nobody treads.

This is the simplest form of the *paritta* ceremony. But there are occasions when *paritta suttas* are simply recited without any accompanying ritual of water or thread. Such is *paritta* recited at the bedside of a dying person. Also where it is inconvenient to have ceremonial paraphernalia, *suttas* alone are recited, as in the case of welcome accorded to State guests, farewells to distinguished persons at their place of departure.

2. Tis Pāye Pirita (The All-Night Paritta Ceremony)

Preparation for this is much more elaborate and it is usually considered an expensive undertaking. Much money is spent on entertaining guests and as a matter of fact the all-night *paritta* ceremony has become a socio-religious festival among wealthy Buddhists.

Monks are invited in the same manner as described above (*See* p. 31). Invitations are also sent out to friends and relations. About a week before the scheduled date the house is given a thorough cleaning ; cobwebs are swept out, the floor is mopped and if mats are used in the household they are washed and dried.

Maṇḍapa

A temporary pavilion called the *pirita maṇḍapa* is erected for this ceremony in a convenient room in the household. The living room is generally chosen for this purpose. The material used for it varies with taste, personnel and money available. Cloth, paper or tender coconut leaves (*gok kola*) are generally used. The shape of the *maṇḍapa* may be a square or an octagon, the framework is made of strips of light wood. It is also possible to hire wooden frames, and the decoration may be done according to individual taste. Once the frame is set up the amateur artist gets ample opportunity to display his imaginative talent. Sometimes paper cut into most exquisite patterns with floral designs or traditional motifs adorns the *parittamaṇḍapa*. Sometimes only tender coconut leaves are used together with strips of plantain trunks and *habara* (*Diospyros ovalifolia*) leaves as accessories. Decoration with this material requires great traditional skill. It is an art which merits special protective measures because there are only a few at present who are versatile in this ancient and intricate art.

Entrance and Its Direction

A *maṇḍapa* usually has one main entrance, but if space permits, it may have four openings on the four sides but only one serves the purpose of an entrance. It is considered auspicious to have the main entrance facing the east or north, but this may be disregarded where convenience demands otherwise

Uḍu Viyana (The Canopy)

The *maṇḍapa* has a white canopy made of freshly laundered cloth (*piruvaṭa*) supported by a network of twine intersecting to form squares of approximately 8 inches in size. On this network, at regular intervals, are hung certain kinds of tender leaves. The varieties traditionally used are said to be the following :—

<i>Nāgavalli</i>	..	Tender betel leaves (<i>Piper betel</i>)
<i>Nāgapallava</i>	..	Tender ironwood leaves (<i>Mesua ferrea</i>)
<i>Nāgalatā</i>	..	Another variety of betel leaves ?
<i>Puvak mal</i>	..	Arecanut flowers (<i>Areca catechu</i>)

According to some informants *siviya dalu*, tender leaves of the *Piper chawya*¹ and *gammiris palukān*, tender leaves of black pepper (*Piper nigrum*), are also used as traditionally recognised decor for the canopy. When it is difficult to secure these varieties, especially in towns, substitutes such as *Bo* (*Ficus religiosa*) and *nuga* (*Ficus bengalensis*) leaves are used.

A row of rings made of tender king coconut leaves (*Cocos nucifera*, variety with pink *epicarp*) runs along the periphery of the canopy on the inner side of the *maṇḍapa* for the thread (*pirit huya*) to pass through when the ceremony begins.

Arrangements inside Maṇḍapa

A table of convenient size is placed in the centre, and chairs are placed all round alongside the framework of the *maṇḍapa*. A minimum of 8 and a maximum of 16 chairs may be used, the exact number chosen being determined by the size of the *maṇḍapa*.² But an odd number of chairs is never used. A small table lower in height is placed next to the other table beside the main entrance. All the chairs and the two tables are covered over with freshly laundered white cloth.

Indrakīla

The two centre chairs directly opposite the main entrance are called *yuga puṭu*, twin chairs. They are tied together and in the centre of the joint is fixed the structure called *indrakīla*. *Rājagaha* is another designation commonly used for the same object ; rarely, it is also referred to as *kapagaha*.

The *indrakīla* (fig 1) is made with a straight freshly cut branch of a *sūriya* tree (*Thespesia populnea*) about 6 feet in length. It is covered over with a stiff white new cloth pleated lengthwise and is tied on to the branch in a couple of places so as to leave the cloth puffing out in between the knots. At the top, the cloth opens out to form a sort of a 'fan.' Sometimes a thin red border is sewn on the outer edge of the 'fan.' Behind this structure stands a small arecanut palm with a fully opened coconut flower. Sometimes the fan-shaped structure and the coconut flower are tied on to the arecanut plant itself. After the *indrakīla* is set up women are not allowed to enter the *parittamaṇḍapa*.

The Indrakīla

Figure 1.

1 Trimen, vol. III, p. 426.

2 Dh. A., vol. II, p. 236. *aṭṭha vā soḷasa vā āsanāni paṭṭāpetvā.*

Karañḍuva (The Casket of Relics)

A place is arranged on the right hand side of the twin chairs above the level of the heads of the monks, to keep the casket containing the relics of the Buddha. If it is very difficult to fix such a place the casket is deposited on the centre table itself. But it is always considered better to place the relics on a higher level.

Pun Kalas

Eight *pun kalas* or vases of plenty as Coomaraswamy calls them,³ are placed round the *maṇḍapa* one at each corner, if it is octagonal in shape. *Kalasa* literally means a pot, but when used for ritual purposes it means a new clay pot in which a coconut flower is placed together with a small coconut oil lamp.

Lada Pas Mal

Five items of ritual import called *lada pas mal* (Pali, *lājapañcamāni pupphāni*, literally meaning five kinds of flowers with roasted paddy as the fifth) are used to sprinkle on the table and inside the *maṇḍapa*. The five items are as follows:—

<i>Ela aba</i>	..	white mustard (<i>Sinapis alba</i>)
<i>Itaṇa</i>	..	panic grass (<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>)
<i>Vilaṇḍa</i> or <i>pori</i>	..	roasted paddy grains (similar to pop corn)
<i>Picca kuppi</i>	..	jasmine buds (<i>Jasminum officinale</i>)
<i>Sun sahal</i>	..	broken rice

Pān Kaḷaya (The Pot of Water)

A new clay pot or a well polished brass pot full of clean strained water is placed on the small table. A fully open coconut flower is placed in the pot, or its mouth is covered with a white kerchief. Often the whole pot is beautifully decorated with tender coconut leaves. Sometimes bottles of medicinal oil, talismans, and even small pots containing sand and pebbles are placed on this table. The belief is that during the ceremony these objects get blessed and charged with power; medicines and talismans are thereby rendered more effective. Sand and stones are used as charms to protect newly built houses.

On the bigger table are placed a vase or tray of fresh flowers, white thread twisted into three strands and wrapped round the panicle of an arecanut flower, a small coconut oil lamp, and some *hañḍun kiri pān* (lit. sandal-milk-water).

Hañḍun Kiri Pān

This mixture is prepared as a purificatory agent to be used by the monks prior to commencement of the ceremony. By custom it is never prepared by a female. A man scrapes some coconut on to a plantain leaf and squeezes it to obtain about half a cup of milk. Into it he adds some sandalwood paste, a piece of raw turmeric and the juice of a lime which has been baked under hot ashes.

Again, as a purificatory measure the whole house is lightly sprinkled over with *kaha diyara* i.e. water mixed with turmeric powder.

³ Coomaraswamy, *Yaksas*, II, pp. 61-63.

The entire *maṇḍapa* is beautifully lit up, or illuminated with small coloured bulbs if electricity is available.

Directly opposite the house a small enclosure made of tender coconut leaves is placed at a height of about 5 feet. It is called the *pahan pāla*, 'oil lamp hut', or *mal pāla*, 'flower hut.' Inside it are placed a few betel leaves on which flowers of various colours are neatly arranged. A clay lamp with coconut oil, incense and camphor are also kept ready to be ignited at the time of the commencement of the ceremony. Once lit the lamp is kept burning until the end of the ceremony.

Plenty of food and soft drinks are provided, and the household is a beehive of activity. Friends and relatives start arriving from early evening. Very close relatives and helpers would have already arrived one or two days previously. Nobody comes empty handed to attend a *paritta* ceremony. Pots of curd, tins of biscuits, great big pineapples, excellent bananas and bunches of king coconuts⁴ are among the most popular gifts that are brought. Usually an all-night *paritta* ceremony is followed by mid-day alms offered to the monks on the following day. The gifts thus brought are utilised at the alms-giving ceremony and for entertaining visitors and neighbours.

All visitors who come to participate in the *paritta* ceremony are generally entertained either with dinner or with light refreshments.

The Ceremony Begins

The chief householder or his deputy goes to fetch the monks from the temple around half past eight in the evening. The monks are generally conducted in a procession accompanied by drummers and other traditional musicians, headed by the chief householder carrying the casket of relics on his head surmounted by a canopy held in place by four other laymen. Nowadays, since cars are freely available, this traditional and colourful part of the ceremony is fast disappearing. The *Paritta* text and the *Pirit huya* are also conveyed from the temple.

When the monks arrive their feet are washed and dried at the entrance as described in the account of the sessional ceremony. A person belonging to the washerman community then spreads a long, narrow white cloth called *pāvāḍa* from the entrance of the house up to the entrance of the *maṇḍapa*. The chief householder (or his deputy) ceremonially conveys the casket of relics placing it on his head, and deposits it in the *maṇḍapa*, on the shelf prepared for it. The monks follow him to the *maṇḍapa*, walking on the *pāvāḍa*.

Everybody present pays homage to the monks. From the time of arrival up to the time when the monks take their seats in the *maṇḍapa*, there is sustained and loud drumming accompanied by the shrill notes of a wind pipe.

After the casket of relics is deposited in place, and the ola leaf manuscript of the *Paritta* text and the *pirit huya* are also placed on the centre table, the monks take their seats according to seniority⁵.

4 The water of the tender nut is considered to possess special health-giving properties.

5 Seniority is reckoned from the date of receiving the higher ordination, *upasampadā*.

The *pirit huya* is an important ritual object consisting of a thick white cord several yards long, wrapped round a large beautifully fashioned bobbin made of sandalwood about 18 inches long. It is always kept in the monastery and is taken to all-night *paritta* ceremonies to which the monks of the temple are invited.

The chief householder offers a tray of betel leaves to the monks and formally invites them to chant the *paritta*. The oil lamps on the *pun kalas* are lit and sticks of burning incense are placed on the coconut flowers which adorn the *kalas*. The monks purify themselves by rubbing their hands with *hañḍun kiri pān*. *Lada pas mal* are lightly sprinkled inside the *maṇḍapa*. The oil lamp in the *pahan pāla* opposite the house is also lit and incense is burnt there.

All devotees sit on mats with hands clasped in salutation and recite the *namaskāra*, after which the chief monk administers *pañca sīla*. He then formally inquires of the chief householder the objective in performing the ceremony. It may be the death anniversary of a parent in which case the ceremony is a memorial service performed for the purpose of dedicating merit to the deceased. Or it may be the approaching wedding of a son or a daughter, or the construction of a new house, and the ceremony is performed for the purpose of invoking blessings. When the objective is made known the monk delivers a short sermon (*anusāsanā*) and commends the householder for spending his time, energy and money on a worthy cause and in the furtherance of a noble objective. The episode regarding the rescue of Vesālī by chanting the *Ratanasutta* is customarily related with a view to illustrating the potency of *paritta* and Buddha's commendation of it. The story of how Prince *Dīghāyu* gained longevity by the power of *paritta* is another favourite theme. It is emphasised that the ceremony which is being presently performed has had a long history, the present performance being the repetition of an age long tradition. The monk concludes his short sermon with the assurance that this ceremony (*piṅkama*, 'meritorious deed') performed with faith and piety will bring blessings to all taking part during this present life and in all lives to come. The chief householder and the other devotees then formally invite the monks gathered in the *maṇḍapa* to commence the chanting of the *paritta*, by reciting thrice a standard verse which runs as follows :—

Vipattiṭṭāhāyā sabbasampattisiddhiyā
sabbadukkhavināsāya parittaṃ brūtha maṅgalaṃ
sabbabhayavināsāya parittaṃ brūtha maṅgalaṃ
sabbarogavināsāya parittaṃ brūtha maṅgalaṃ

Tr. "Be pleased to recite the noble *paritta*, for the warding off of calamities, the accomplishment of all prosperity and the destruction of all sorrow, fear and ill-health."

The drummers now start to beat their drums in a prescribed beat (*magul bera*) for a few minutes. Simultaneously with its dramatic conclusion the monks start chanting the *paritta* in chorus. The suttas chanted are as follows :

- | | |
|--------------------------------|--|
| (1) <i>Samantā cakkavāḷesu</i> | .. Invitation to the gods to come and listen to the <i>paritta</i> |
| (2) <i>Namaskāra</i> | .. Salutation to Buddha |
| (3) <i>Paṭiccasamuppāda</i> | .. Dependent origination (optional) |
| (4) <i>Iti pi so Bhagavā</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Buddha</i> |
| (5) <i>Svākkhāto</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Dhamma</i> |

- | | | |
|------------------------------------|----|--|
| (6) <i>Supaṭipanno</i> | .. | Adoration of <i>Saṅgha</i> |
| (7) <i>Jayamaṅgalagāthā</i> | .. | Invocation of blessings by the power of Buddha |
| (8) <i>Bhavatu sabbamaṅgalam</i> | .. | Benedictory refrains |
| (9) <i>Nakkhattayakkhabhūtānaṃ</i> | .. | do. |

The chanting up to this point is called *pirit pē kirima* i.e. performance of rites preliminary to *paritta*. This stops for a while and drummers start beating their drums again. All the monks stand up and tie the *pirit huya* in the manner described below, while reciting the following formula :—

*Sabbe Buddhā balappattā
paccekānañ ca yaṃ balaṃ
arahantānañ ca tejena
rakkhaṃ bandhāmi sabbaso*

Tr. "All Buddhas have attained great powers, and so have *Paccekabuddhas* and *Arahants*. By the majesty of their powers I tie this protection valid all round."

It is tied connecting the casket of Relics, the *Paritta* text, the pot of water and the *indrakila*. It is then taken up to the canopy and passed through the rings made of tender king coconut leaves fixed on the periphery of the canopy, in a clockwise direction. When it has fully encircled the canopy it is brought down and passed through the hands of all the monks before it is finally placed back on the table. The *pirit nūla*, i.e. the three-strand thread wrapped round the panicle of an arecanut flower is connected to the *pirit huya* at some point near the canopy. It is taken out of the *maṇḍapa* and given to the devotees who are sitting around. Unwinding the skein they pass round, each person holding the thread with hands clasped in salutation, taking care not to let the thread touch the ground. Thus, by means of this *paritta* thread all devotees get connected with the *Buddha* represented by the relics⁶, the *Dhamma* represented by the *Paritta* text, the *Saṅgha* represented by the monks, and the *indrakila*, the symbolism of which will be considered later on.

After the *pirit huya* and the *pirit nūla* are thus arranged, drumming ends and the monks resume chanting in chorus. This phase is called *mahapirita* or the great *paritta* and it includes the recitation of the following *suttas* :—

- (1) *Mahāmaṅgalasutta* (or *Dhajaggasutta*) ;
- (2) *Ratanasutta* ;
- (3) *Karaṇiyamettasutta* ;
- (4) Benedictory refrains (*yaṃ dunnimittaṃ . . . , dukkhappattā . . . , sabbe buddhā balappattā . . .*).

The *mahapirita* is considered to be the most important phase of the ceremony and the maximum number of devotees gather to listen to it. After the *mahapirita* is over, the *pirit nūla* is folded and placed back on the centre table in the *maṇḍapa* or on a *kalasa*. The visitors are now entertained with refreshments, many of the guests go away while close friends and relatives remain all night.

⁶ Vbh. A., p. 431—*dhātusu hi ṭhitāsu Buddhā ṭhitā va honti*. "The presence of the relics is equivalent to the presence of the Buddha."

Throughout the ceremony the monks are supplied readily with plain tea or fruit juice whenever the necessity arises. A couple of men are specially entrusted with the task of attending on the monks. A neatly arranged plate of raisins, candy (*sūkiri* and *talsūkiri*), jaggery and ginger is placed on the table inside the *maṇḍapa* so that the monks can help themselves whenever they need to whet their throats during the chanting.

After the *mahapirita* all the monks except two, leave. These two monks continue the chanting and this phase is called the *yuga pirita*, i.e. twin *paritta*. Section IV of the *Paritta* text, commonly called *sūtra deśanā*, is chanted during this period. This *yuga pirita* generally starts around 11.00 p.m. and goes on till about 3.00 a.m., the monks being relieved in pairs, every hour.

When the *yuga pirita* comes to a close, the drumming starts again. Four monks enter the *maṇḍapa* and the two who were there leave. No sooner does the drumming cease than the monks start chanting the *Āṭānāṭṭiyasutta*. This is a *sutta* particularly recommended by *yakkha* leaders for recitation by Buddhist monks to bring stubborn and vicious demons (*yakkhas*) under control. As stated earlier, the commentary on this *sutta*⁷ requires that monks reciting it should abstain from eating pastries and meats (*piṭṭhaṃ vā maṅsaṃ vā*), and should avoid visiting cemeteries because demons (*amanussā*, lit. non-humans) would find opportunities to harm them (*otāraṃ labhanti*). Though not all the traditional observances recommended in the commentary are adhered to at present, recitation of the *Āṭānāṭṭiya* is still treated with special care and attention. Parents would take care to see that children do not go out of the house during its recitation. In some areas much noise is made by striking metal betel trays with arecanut cutters or by jingling bunches of keys. The monks too recite the *Āṭānāṭṭiya* much louder than the other *suttas*. The *sutta* itself lays down that it should be recited very loud.⁸ In short, the tone of the ceremony during this phase, is suggestive of its purpose, namely exorcism. This *sutta* is popularly known as the *hamāra* which means 'the conclusion.'

After the *hamāra* around 5.00 a.m., all the monks assemble in the *maṇḍapa* again and the following *suttas* are recited :

- | | |
|---|--|
| (1) <i>Karaṇīyamettasutta</i> | .. Expression of universal benevolence |
| (2) <i>Yaṃ dunnimittaṃ</i> | .. Benedictory refrains |
| (3) <i>Dukkhaṃ pappā ca</i> | .. do. |
| (4) <i>Sabbhe buddhā</i> | .. Formula for tying the protective thread |
| (5) <i>Mahājīnapaṅkajā</i> | .. Great cage of the Conqueror |
| (6) <i>Aṭṭavīsi pirita</i> | .. <i>Paritta</i> of 28 Buddhas |
| (7) <i>Mahājayaṃāṅgalagāthā</i> | .. The great poem for success and prosperity |
| (8) <i>Cetiyaṃ pūjā</i> (e.g. <i>Vandāmi cetiyaṃ</i>) | .. <i>Stūpa</i> worship |
| (9) <i>Patthanā gāthā</i> (e.g. <i>Iminā puññakammaṇa</i>) | .. Aspiration |
| (10) <i>Upajjhāyā guṇuttarā</i> | .. Aspiration |
| (11) <i>Samākaragānīma</i> (<i>kāyena vācā</i>) | .. Prayer for remission |
| (12) <i>Okāsa dvārattayena</i> | .. Prayer for remission |

7 DA. vol. III, p. 969.

D. vol. III, p. 205 : *ujjhāpetabbaṃ vikkanditabbaṃ viravitabbaṃ*. PSPP., p. xxx.

The ceremony comes to an end around 5.30 a.m. with the distribution of *paritta* water and thread. A monk takes some water from the decorated pot into a smaller container. The chief householder, or the person for whom the ceremony is specially performed, is summoned near the entrance to the *maṇḍapa*. All monks recite three stanzas from the *Ratanasutta* extolling the virtues of the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Saṅgha*. *Yaṃ kiñci vittaṃ*⁹, *Yaṃ buddhaseṭṭho*,¹⁰ and *Ye puggalā*¹¹, are the three stanzas traditionally chosen for this occasion. This is followed by benedictory refrains such as *Sabbṭṭiyo vivaṃjantu*....., *Bhavatu sabhamāṅgalaṃ*....., *Nakkhattayakkhabhūtānaṃ*....¹² During this recitation one monk slowly pours *paritta* water into the hands of the devotee who reverentially sips some of it and rubs the rest on his face and head. After the chief householder, others follow suit. Then the monk takes a piece of the *pīrit nūla* moistens it with the *paritta* water and ties it round the chief householder's forearm or wrist. *Iti pi so bhagavā*..... (i.e. adoration of the Buddha), and *Sabbe buddhā balappattā*.... (a benedictory refrain) are recited while tying the thread. Other male devotees follow suit.

The monks then return to the monastery, and the morning meal is generally prepared and sent to the monastery. But if it is intended to conclude the ceremony with the morning meal (*hīl dāne*) it is offered to the monks in the house itself. Nearly always an all-night *paritta* ceremony is followed by a mid-day offering of alms to the monks.

Seats for the monks at the almsgiving consist of cushions arranged along the walls of the dining room and covered with white cloth. The meal is also arranged on a white cloth spread on a mat in front of the seats. The individual dishes are covered with discs cut out of banana leaves, and the whole array of dishes is covered with a white cloth.

Monks are conducted around 10.30 a.m. While drum music is going on, their feet are washed and dried at the entrance. The monks occupy the seats according to seniority and the drumming ceases when all have sat down. First of all, a meal is offered to the Buddha by placing food and drink in front of the relics (*buddhapūjā*) and all devotees sit down with hands clasped in salutation. One monk, generally the seniormost, requests the devotees to say the *namaskāra*. The devotees generally get permission for themselves by merely saying "May it please you Sirs" (*avasarayi*) and start reciting the formula *Namo tassa bhagavato*....etc. The monk then 'gives' *pansil* and the devotees 'take' by repeating the same, and offer the *buddhapūjā* with the appropriate stanza, namely,

*Adhivāsetu no bhante pāṇiyaṃ|bhojanaṃ parikappitaṃ
anukampaṃ upādāya patignahātu-m-uttama*

Tr. "Please accept Reverend Sir the drink and food which has been prepared
Out of sympathy (for us) may the Noble One accept (this offering)."

After this the monk delivers a short sermon extolling the nobility of the meritorious deeds performed so far, from the previous night onwards. Merit of *paritta* and *dāna* (charity) are illustrated with episodes taken from the Canon. At the end, the alms are formally dedicated to the *Saṅgha* by repeating the following formula thrice :

Imaṃ bhikkhaṃ sapaṛikkhāraṃ bhikkhusaṅghassa dema

9 Sn., v. 224.

10 Sn., v. 226.

11 Sn., v. 227.

12 See above for translation. p. 25

Tr. "We give this alms together with other requisites to the Community of monks."¹³ After this formal dedication the devotees get up and start serving the monks. The meal is uncovered and water is offered first of all. Both males and females can take part in serving the meal. With quiet dignity, the monks partake of the meal which consists of rice and curry, followed by a dessert. Fruits, sweetmeats, curd and treacle are served as dessert. The meal is concluded before noon and gifts of requisites are formally presented. It is customary to offer some appropriate useful gift to each of the monks at the end of a *sāṅghikadāna*, i.e. an alms-giving dedicated to the entire Community of monks: Betel leaves together with the accompanying ingredients are also offered.

Then follows the *puññānumodanā*, the dedication of merit. A special ritual is performed to dedicate merit to the departed relatives. The chief householder takes a jug of water together with another empty bowl placed on a plate or a tray. Generally the bowl chosen for this purpose is smaller than the jug as the water poured into the bowl must overflow its brim. The householder holds the jug of water above the bowl and pours it out slowly as the monks recite the following:—

*Unname udakaṃ vaṭṭhaṃ yathā ninnaṃ pavattati
evam eva ito dinnāṃ peṭānaṃ upakappatu
Yathā vārivahā pūrā paripūrenti sāgaram
evam eva ito dinnāṃ peṭānaṃ upakappatu*

Tr. "Rain water fallen on high ground flows down to lower levels. Similarly may what is given from here reach the departed ones. Just as swollen rivers fill up the ocean, even so may the merit dedicated from here reach the departed ones."

While the monks recite thus, the householder slowly pours the water from the jug into the bowl and it is so timed that when the monks recite the formula for the third time the small bowl is overflowing with water.

Merit is then dedicated to the relatives with following formula too, recited thrice by the whole congregation of monks and laymen :—

*Idaṃ me nātīnaṃ hotu, sukhitā hontu nātayo*¹⁴

Tr. "May this merit accrue to my relatives, May they be well and happy."

On occasions when the water ritual is not enacted, the above formula alone is repeated thrice.

Merit is then dedicated to the gods, spirits and all creatures :

*Ettāvātā ca amhehi sambhataṃ puññasampadaṃ
sabbe devā|bhūtā¹⁵,|sattā anumodantu sabbasampattisiddhiyā.*

Tr. "May the merit accumulated by us as a result of these good deeds be shared by all deities, all non-human beings and all creatures, and may they ensure prosperity (for us)."

13 By 'other requisites' is meant other appropriate gifts offered to the monks at the end of the meal, such as robes, towels, bowls, slippers, umbrellas, fans, soap etc.

14 The monks recite this formula as *Idaṃ vo nātīnaṃ hotu...* meaning 'May this merit accrue to your relatives...' The subsequent formulae for the dedication of merit too are recited in unison by both monks and laymen.

15 Several meanings are recorded in Kh. A., p. 166 : *idha pana amanussesu daṭṭhabbo.*

*Ākāsaṅṅhā ca bhūmmaṅṅhā devā nāgā mahiddhikā
puññam tam anumoditvā ciraṃ rakkhantu sāsanaṃ/desanaṃ/maṃ paraṃ*

Tr. "May all deities and *nāgas* of mighty power, residing in the air and on earth, accept this merit and protect the dispensation of the Buddha, teachings of the Buddha, me and all others."

This is generally followed by the aspiration. The monk says in Sinhala : "As a result of the noble meritorious deeds performed, such as listening to the *paritta*, offering alms etc., may all devotees who took part directly and indirectly, attain to greater and greater prosperity day by day. Having enjoyed health, wealth and good fortune during a long span of life may you all be born in celestial spheres. May you never suffer birth in any woeful state. After having enjoyed human and celestial pleasures for a very long time may you attain the deathless tranquility of *Nirvāna* during the dispensation of the Future Buddha, *Maitreya*."

All devotees present rejoice in these words and exclaim " *sādhu sādhu sādhu*."¹⁶

The ceremony is over, the monks receive obeisance from everybody present, and they depart, taking with them the casket of relics, the *Paritta* text and the *pirit huya*.

Now starts the social aspect of the ceremony. All visitors and neighbours are entertained to lunch. No tables are set up, it is customary to sit on mats and enjoy the meal. The washermen and the drummers are fed in a separate corner of the verandah. All others sit together on mats without any distinction and heartily enjoy a very sumptuous meal.

Paritta water and thread are freely given without ceremony to anybody who wants it. Everybody is in a happy and relaxed mood. The chief householder and his wife are generally very tired, but the fatigue is only physical due to lack of sleep the previous night and the amount of work put in for preparation of food and entertainment. But mentally they are very happy that they have successfully carried through a great meritorious performance, a performance which grants prosperity for the present and security for the future.

Disposal of Material

Traditionally the *paritta maṅḍapa* is not demolished until one and a half days pass,¹⁷ but there is no hard and fast rule regarding the disposal of material with the exception of the coconut flowers. *Paritta* water and thread are generally kept until the third day and neither is disposed of in a place where people tread. Any food remaining from dishes that were formally dedicated to the *Saṅgha* with the formula beginning *Imaṃ bhikkhaṃ* is carefully thrown away. Such food, however clean, is never used for entertaining lay devotees. It may be given to an animal though; beggars also partake of it. The idea is that anything offered to the monks with that special formula belongs to the Community and it is not proper for a layman to partake of it hereafter.

The coconut flowers which adorned the pot of water and the *indrakila* are carefully stored away in a very high place, generally the ceiling, of the house. They are believed to bring good luck and prosperity. Villagers carry them to the fields with great delight, and there hoist them on long sticks and plant them in the middle of the field. The belief is strong that this ensures a bountiful harvest and freedom from pestilence.

¹⁶ The Buddhist equivalent of Christian 'Amen.'

¹⁷ *tun varuvak*, three sessions, i.e. evening of the same day plus the morning and evening of the following day.

The oil lamp in the *pahan pāla* outside the house continues to be lit for three consecutive nights. The *pahan pāla* itself is not generally removed ; it is allowed to wither there.

3. Sati Pīrita (The Seven Day Paritta Ceremony)

The seven day *paritta* ceremony is customarily known as *baṇapīrit* (lit. *paritta* discourse), and is mostly held in monasteries. But there is nothing to prevent the performance of such a ceremony in a private household if all facilities can be provided. A *maṇḍapa* is constructed in the same manner as for the all-night ceremony, but with more durable material. The *indrakīla* described above is a ritual object particularly set up for seven day ceremonies, even though it is used for all-night ceremonies as well.

Lay supporters (*dāyakaḃ*) raise funds for the ceremony by public subscription, and they appoint a committee of capable men to be in charge of various duties connected with the ceremony.

As a seven day *paritta* ceremony is a joint effort of the clergy and the laity it calls for greater co-operation and co-ordination of duties. Therefore, tradition has drawn up a *baṇapīrit katikāvata*, i.e. a convention incorporating the duties of laymen and clergy regarding a *baṇapīrita*¹. It is convenient to summarise the content of this convention here, as it gives a clear picture of the roles played by respective participants and the proceedings approved by tradition.

Duties of the Laymen

Lay supporters wishing to have a seven day *paritta* ceremony performed should respectfully communicate their intention to the chief monk of the temple and invite at least 25 monks. They should make arrangements to supply the monks with all requirements for seven days, such as regular meals, refreshments, lodgings, sanitary facilities, transport etc. From the commencement of the ceremony one or more responsible laymen should be appointed to carry out each of the following duties :

- (1) to serve the monks in the *maṇḍapa* ;
- (2) to provide drum music at proper times ;
- (3) to maintain orderly behaviour among devotees ;
- (4) to take messages for *yugapīrit* ;
- (5) to look after the safety of the monks ;
- (6) to arrange for a *dēvadūtayā* ²
- (7) to organise orderly collection of subscriptions, keep accounts and set them aside for temple use ;
- (8) to prevent unruly gathering, drinking of liquor and gambling in the immediate neighbourhood ;
- (9) to co-ordinate processions, if any, coming from neighbouring villages ;
- (10) to distribute without partiality all gifts donated by the devotees, among monks, with the consent of the committee of monks.

1 *Banapīrit katikāvata* was formally constituted by a 30 member committee headed by Ven. *Tibhatuvave Sri Siddhārtha Sumaṅgala*, Ven. *Vaṭarāka Ratanajoti Sobhita*, and Ven. *Anukkane Saṅgharakkhite SaranāṅkaraTheras* in 1906. See PSPP. pp. xi, 273-284.

2 See below p. 46.

Duties of the Monks

A monk should not accept an invitation for a seven day *paritta* ceremony without first consulting his teacher and preceptor. After proper acceptance it is his obligation to attend the ceremony punctually.

Monks should advise the laymen regarding the construction of the *maṇḍapa*, arrangements for lodgings, procedure of the ceremony, and they should also train the *dēvadūtayā*, the messenger to the gods. In all dealings with the laity monks should keep at a respectable distance aloof from them. Their behaviour should in no way engender disrespect in the laity.

When participating in the ceremony monks should conduct themselves with pious dignity and decorum. In chanting *paritta* they should not try to excel one another as if in a competition. They should not band themselves into groups and indulge in frivolous talk. In all matters they should work with unity, amity and dignity. When one's turn comes for *yugapirit* etc. one should diligently attend to one's duty without offering excuses of ill health. In case of genuine ill health, the monk in charge of arrangements must be notified early so that alternative arrangements could be made without inconvenience.

First Day

An assembly of all monks participating in the ceremony is convened in the morning of the day scheduled for the ceremony to begin. With the unanimous consent of the *Saṅgha*, monks are appointed to carry out the following duties :

- (1) to preside at the opening session ;
- (2) to write the *vihāra asna*, i.e. the message from the monastery, and the *dēvālapata*, i.e. letter to the shrine of gods ;
- (3) to supervise the role of *dēvadūtayā*, the messenger to the gods ;
- (4) to play the role of *anuśāsaka bhikṣu*, i.e. to admonish the gods ;
- (5) to deliver sermons (more than one may be appointed for the different days) ;
- (6) to arrange a time table for *yuga pirit*, giving names, dates and times ; and attend to the purificatory measures of the *maṇḍapa* (*tēvāva bhikṣu*).

All this is formally written down in the form of a document and signed by the chief incumbent. A committee representing the *Saṅgha* is then appointed to deal with all aspects and problems of this joint arrangement of the *Saṅgha* and laity. The office bearers mentioned earlier are also included in this committee. The main task of this body is to ensure that all proceedings are carried out smoothly. Should any differences of opinion arise among the sponsors or members of the lay committee, it is the duty of the *Saṅgha* committee to intervene and settle disputes amicably. The committee also has to bear the responsibility of making alternative arrangements in case the time table already fixed cannot be strictly followed due to unavoidable circumstances. In short the committee has to ensure the smooth uninterrupted performance of the ceremony by eliminating all shortcomings and making adequate provision for any emergencies.

Dēvadūtayā—The Messenger to the Gods

At the time preliminary arrangements are made for the *paritta* ceremony a young boy about ten years old is chosen to play the role of the messenger to the gods. Generally a handsome smart boy with a good clear voice is selected. A princely costume is made ready for him, and it consists of a bright silk dhoti, a beautifully embroidered jacket, a pointed golden crown, and

plenty of jewellery. The boy memorises the *dorakaḍa asna* (lit. the message at the threshold) and practises it daily to be able to deliver it freely on the seventh day of the ceremony. From the commencement of the ceremony he has to reside in the monastery and also wait upon the monks chanting *paritta*. He is treated with special attention by the laity throughout the period of the ceremony.

The Ceremony Begins

Monks enter the *maṇḍapa* walking on the *pāvāḍa* one after the other, in the same manner as for the all-night ceremony, after having had their feet washed and dried at the entrance. The relic casket leads the procession of monks ; the *pirit huya* and the *paritta* text are also taken along. Drum music goes on continuously until all monks have taken their seats.

After 'giving' *pansil* to the devotees the monks themselves clasp their hands in salutation and recite the following suttas :

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| (1) <i>Paṭiccasamuppāda</i> | .. Dependent origination |
| (2) <i>Anekajāṭisaṃsāraṃ</i> | .. First words of the Buddha expressing joy |
| (3) <i>Iti pi so bhagavā</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Buddha</i> |
| (4) <i>Svākkhāto</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Dhamma</i> |
| (5) <i>Supaṭipanno</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Saṅgha</i> |
| (6) <i>Jayamaṅgalagāthā</i> | .. Invocation of blessings by the majesty of Buddha's victory over fierce opponents |
| (7) <i>Bhavatu sabbamaṅgalam</i> | .. Benedictory refrain |
| (8) <i>Nakkhatta yakkhabhūtānaṃ</i> | .. Benedictory refrain |

When these eight suttas are chanted, drums beat again for a while, after which the monks resume chanting the following :

- | | |
|--|--|
| (9) <i>Karaṇṭyametta Sutta</i> | .. Universal benevolence |
| (10) <i>Ratanasutta</i> (stanzas 3-14) | .. Invocation of blessings by the power of <i>Buddha</i> , <i>Dhamma</i> and <i>Saṅgha</i> |
| (11) <i>Yaṃ dunnimittaṃ</i> | .. Benedictory refrain |
| (12) <i>Dukkappattā ca niddukkhā</i> | .. Benedictory refrain |
| (13) <i>Sabbe Buddhā</i> | .. Formula used for tying <i>paritta</i> thread |

While reciting the last stanza all monks get up and connect the *pirit huya* with the relic casket, *paritta* text, pot of water and the *indrakīla* and draw it through the rings in the canopy in a clockwise direction to make a complete circle as in the case of the all-night ceremony. One monk sprinkles *paritta* water in and around the *maṇḍapa*. Drums beat again for a while and the monks sit down again and chant the following with hands clasped in salutation :

- | | |
|-------------------------------------|--|
| (14) <i>Namo tassa bhagavato</i> | .. Salutation to <i>Buddha</i> |
| (15) <i>Iti pi so bhagavā</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Buddha</i> |
| (16) <i>Buddham jvitapariyantaṃ</i> | .. Confession of faith in <i>Buddha</i> for life |
| (17) <i>Svākkhāto bhagavatā</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Dhamma</i> |
| (18) <i>Dhammaṃ jvitapariyantaṃ</i> | .. Confession of faith in <i>Dhamma</i> for life |
| (19) <i>Supaṭipanno</i> | .. Adoration of <i>Saṅgha</i> |
| (20) <i>Saṅghaṃ jvitapariyantaṃ</i> | .. Confession of faith in <i>Saṅgha</i> for life |
| (21) <i>Buddha dhammā ca</i> | .. Invocation of <i>Buddha</i> and <i>Dhamma</i> to release one's mind from evil |

Proceedings up to this point are described as *pirita pé kirīma* in Sinhala, which means the performance of preliminary rites. The monks then wet their hands with *hañḍum kiri pān* and this itself is another purificatory measure. The two monks who are scheduled to start the chanting the following morning occupy the two centre chairs (*yuga puṭṭu*) and the others formally invite them to chant *paritta*, with the following stanza :

*Vipattiṭṭapaṭibāhāya sabbasampattisiddhiyā
sabbadukkhavināsāya parittam brūtha maṅgalaṃ
sabbabhayavināsāya parittam brūtha maṅgalaṃ
sabbharogavināsāya parittam brūtha maṅgalaṃ*

Tr. " Please chant the auspicious *paritta* to ward off adversity and invite prosperity.
Please chant the auspicious *paritta* to dispel all suffering, fear and disease."

Drums beat for a while after which the two monks occupying the two centre chairs start chanting the following suttas³

- (1) *Namaskāraya*
- (2) *Saraṇāgamaṇa*
- (3) *Namaskāraya*
- (4) *Dasa sila*
- (5) *Sāmaneraṇāṭṭha*
- (6) *Dvattiṃsākāra*
- (7) *Paccavekkhaṇā*
- (8) *Dasadhammasutta*.

Then all monks join to chant the *mahāpirita* which consists of the following suttas :

- (1) *Mahāmaṅgalasutta*
- (2) *Ratanasutta*
- (3) *Karaṇīyamettasutta*
- (4) *Mahājayamaṅgalagāthā* (*gāthās* 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 8 and 9 only)
- (5) Benedictory refrains.

All monks leave except the two continuing the *yuga pirita*. Every hour or every two hours the monks are relieved by two others and chanting goes on continuously. Thrice a day morning, noon and evening the *mahāpirita* is chanted by all monks and each of these sessions is heralded by drum music. This pattern of *yugapirit* and *mahāpirit* is repeated until the 6th day

Third Day

Distribution of *paritta* water starts on the third day evening. Apart from this everything else goes on in the same manner up to the sixth day with non-stop chanting.

Sixth Day

This is a special day. In the evening the *maṅḍapa* is redecorated with fresh flowers and leaves. The *lada pas mal* is removed and a fresh supply is sprinkled. The leaves on the canopy and the coconut flowers in the *kalas* are changed. After redoing the *maṅḍapa* in this manner a monk announces *sūtra dēśanā*, which means *suttas* chanted on this day are different to those which have been chanted so far. The seven *suttas* which form an appendix to *Catubhāṇavārapāḷi* are chanted in the order in which they are arranged in the *paritta* text. Beating of drums heralds this *sūtra dēśanā*.

³ See above p. 5-11.

Seventh Day

As on other days *mahapīṛita* is chanted by all monks in the morning and two monks continue the *yuga pīṛita*. Around 9 a.m. all the monks assemble in the *maṇḍapa* again, and all hold the *pīṛit huya*. *Yuga pīṛita* is temporarily stopped, and the two monks sit silently in their seats. The monk who has been appointed to write the *dēvālapata*, i.e. the letter to the shrine of the gods, takes his stand on the right side of the table and announces the almanac (*lita kiyavanavā*, i.e. the year, month, day, date, hour, moment and planetary conjunctions of the moment. Then the *anuśāsaka bhikṣu*, the monk who is appointed to admonish the gods, stands on the left side of the table and starts writing the *vihāra asna*, the message from the monastery. He then reads out what he wrote. The former then writes out the *dēvālapata* while standing there itself and reads it out. Once the task of writing out the two messages is over all except two leave and *yuga pīṛita* resumes.

Vihāra Asna⁴

This is a long document running to about two and a half printed pages. The message in short is as follows :

“Today a *paritta* ceremony takes place in this monastery. The Community of monks unanimously requests that all deities residing in various shrines, temples etc. (a long list is mentioned by place names and this makes the document quite long) come and listen to the *maṅgalasutta* etc. and share in the merit thereof. They must not disobey the orders of the Community of monks and they must come together with their retinues.”

Devālapata⁵

This is a shorter document and it is an individual invitation to the gods residing in a particular shrine close to the monastery where the ceremony is conducted. Its message is as follows :—

“Today *pīṛit* is being chanted in this monastery which is close to such and such a shrine of the gods. The Community of monks desires that all gods residing in this *dēvāla* should come without exception together with their retinues. They must come without disobeying the order of the Community.”

Before evening five palm leaf copies of these two documents are made. In the evening monks assemble again in or around the *maṇḍapa* and screen off a portion of it or the whole *maṇḍapa*. They take the messenger to the gods too into the enclosure, now fully dressed in his special princely costume with crown on head. Here the monks tie the *dēvālakada*, the pingo for the abode of gods. It is also called *hēmakada*, the golden pingo. One copy of each document is left in the *maṇḍapa*. The other four copies are rolled up, sprinkled over with turmeric water and lightly fumigated with burning incense. After this ritual cleansing, the scrolls are placed in the small pingo decorated with sprigs of betel leaves (*bulat palukān*) and arecanut flowers. The messenger is accompanied by two, four, or eight attendants called *doraṭupālayō*—they are boys around ten years of age, dressed in beautiful dhoti and jacket, but not as grandly as the

4 PSPP. p. 284.

5 *ibid.* p. 287.

messenger. They carry swords and stand as guards on either side of the messenger. The *anuśāsaka bhikṣu*, the monk designated to admonish the gods, 'gives' *pansil* to the messenger, his attendants and the retinue accompanying him to the *dēvālaya*, and gives them *paritta* water. He then hands over to the messenger a small decanter of *paritta* water, oil, flowers, incense and other articles of worship. Finally he entrusts to him the *hēmakada* containing the message to be delivered to the gods.

The procession sets out with drums beating. The messenger is flanked by his attendants and surrounded by people carrying swords, flags and banners. Sometimes the procession is organised on such a grand scale as to take the messenger on elephant back (Plate VIII) or in a beautifully decorated cart. Many of the devotees going in the procession carry flags and banners, and ceremonial articles such as flowers, oil and incense. They take a circuitous route and arrive at the shrine indicated in the letter. There they worship, offer flowers, light oil lamps and burn incense. The messenger to the gods recites *Jayamaṅgalagāthā* and enters the inner chamber of the shrine and reads out the message in a loud clear voice. After this he deposits the four copies meant for the four guardian deities. . . . *Dhṣṭarāṣṭra*, *Virūḍha*, *Vīṭipākṣa* and *Vaiśravaṇa* in four places. As there are no special shrines dedicated to them, generally the four copies are hung on the four sides of the *bodhi* tree. The mission is now fulfilled and the procession returns to the *parittamaṅḍapa*.

When the procession of the messenger departs and the sound of drums can no longer be heard the monks in the *maṅḍapa* chant *mahapirit* and distribute *paritta* water. When the beating of drums is heard again on the return journey of the messenger, two monks start chanting *Mahāsamayāsutta* which includes an enumeration of the Buddha's celestial retinue.

When the messenger arrives his feet are washed and dried at the entrance to the hall. A *pāvāḍa* is spread and he walks on it up to the entrance to the *parittamaṅḍapa*. There he stands at the threshold holding the doorposts on either side. His attendants stand behind him clasping their hands in salutation. They are given *paritta* water to drink and the *paritta* thread to hold and the *anuśāsaka bhikṣu* stands up and asks the following question :

" Are there people at the entrance to this beautiful decorated *maṅḍapa* ? "

Messenger replies :—

" There are people at the entrance to this beautiful *dharma maṅḍapa* which is built to resemble a celestial mansion, elegantly decorated by men of pure faith.

The monk questions :

" Has the messenger returned who went to invite the great gods ? "

Messenger replies :

" The messenger to the gods who was instructed by the pious virtuous monks assembled in this beautiful *maṅḍapa*, has returned. The messenger who had dedicated himself for this mission, and who had prepared himself with devotion for seven days has fulfilled his obligation and returned together with his retinue."

The monk questions again :

" Have the gods come headed by *Vaiśravaṇa* who adorns the lotus throne of variegated beauty? "

He returns by the
The K. S. S.

Messenger replies :

“ Gods have come together with their retinues to listen to the noble doctrine in order to get rid of all sorrow. Gods endowed with majestic power, splendour and might, gods who dwell on mountains, plateaux and plains, and those residing in the atmosphere, gods of greater and lesser powers . . . they have all come.”

After giving this reply, the messenger goes on to deliver the *dorakaḍa asna*, the message at the threshold for which he has been specially trained.

Dorakaḍa Asna⁶ (Message at the Threshold)

The full text of this message is almost impossible to translate. The rhetorical language is so highly ornate and the vocabulary so pedantic and Sanskritised that it is extremely difficult to understand the actual message without making a proper study of its text. The whole speech abounds in much alliteration and rhymes so as to create a sort of mystic glow round the message and the messenger as well.

Though the text of the message would run into two full printed pages its essence is that all gods of mighty power including the four great guardian gods have come together with their retinues.

When the messenger finishes this announcement of the arrival of the gods, the *anusāsaka* monk whose duty is to admonish the gods starts his impressive speech. This is no second to the former in its oratorical ostentation.

Anusāsanāva⁷ (Admonition)

An abridged version of the admonition is as follows :—

“ Pious monks have chanted the *Maṅgalasutta* preached by the Blessed One of supreme virtue, knowledge and majesty. May the gods rejoice and share in the merit produced thereby.

For seven days and seven nights faithful devotees have honoured and attended on the *Buddha*, *Dhamma* and *Śaṅgha*. May the gods rejoice and share in the merit produced thereby.

Alms were offered to the monks who are direct descendants of *Sāriputta* and *Moggallāna*. May the gods rejoice and share in the merit produced thereby.

All gods in the sphere of sense pleasures and in the sphere of form including *Sakra*, *Brahma*, *Viṣṇu* and *Maheśvara* also must share in the merit.

All gods residing on mountains such as *Meru*, *Yugandhara* etc. also must share in the merit.

Gods presiding over the nine planets dwelling in celestial abodes in space also must share in the merit.

Twenty seven gods presiding over 27 constellations . . .

Gods presiding over Sri Lanka—*Utpalavarṇa*, *Sumana*, *Kārtikēya*, *Vibhīṣaṇa* and deities of the 4 shrines . . .

6 PSPP., p. 288

7 *ibid.* p. 290.

Deities presiding over *Kajāṅgala* . . . *Vepulla* etc.

Guardians of the eight directions such as *Indra*, *Soma*, *Agni* etc.

Twenty eight leaders of *Yakṣas* such as *Indra*, *Soma*, *Varuṇa*, *Bhūradvāja*, *Prajāpati* etc.

Group deities (*gaṇadevatā* such as *Āditya*, *Vasu* etc.)

Hosts of *bhūtas* (non-human beings) such as *Puṣpadanta*, *Urvaśya* etc.

All deities residing in *bodhi* trees, *stūpas*, shrine rooms, villages, groves, monasteries, cities, forests, woodlands, lakes, rivers, seas, celestial abodes etc.

Deities residing in huge trees such as banyan, rose apple, margosa etc. etc.

Deities residing in rivers such as *Gaṅgā*, *Yamunā* etc.

Goddess *Maṇimekhalā* of great beauty

Earth goddess

Goddess *Sarasvatī*

Demons headed by *Vepacitti*

Great *nāgas* such as *Sanḥkhapāla*, *Mahākāla* etc.

Numerous gods residing in water, land, trees, mountains etc.

May all these gods mentioned above rejoice and share in the meritorious deeds performed and attain to greater glory and prosperity. Sharing in the merit in this manner they should consider it their duty to reprimand and hold in check the malevolent demons who are ill disposed towards these devotees who have performed this meritorious deed. Let them remove all ills such as physical and mental ailments arising from unfavourable planetary conjunctions. Let them promote longevity, health, wealth and prosperity.

If there are any stubborn malevolent demons who do not listen to the advice of gods, for the purpose of bringing them under control, monks would chant the *Āṭānāṭiyasutta* which has been recommended by the Four Great Guardian Deities themselves, and it can by no means be ignored by the demons.

Guard and guide these pious devotees. Ward off all evil befalling them from climatic vicissitudes, enemies, demons, wild animals, venomous snakes, unfavourable planetary movements, evil dreams, wicked omens, quarrels and hostile arguments. Bring them all success, prosperity and happiness."

When this admonition is over people make offerings of various appropriate articles such as robes, bowls, umbrellas, slippers, books, towels, soap etc. etc. to the monks. They also show their appreciation of the messenger by showering various gifts on him too. A subscription bowl also goes round among the devotees and all make small contributions according to their means.

The time is now set for the *Āṭānāṭiyasutta*. Four monks seat themselves, two on either side with two *Paritta* texts and chant the sutta. Special effort is made for distinct enunciation of words, and chanting is done with great vigour and intonation.

At dawn all monks assemble in the *maṇḍapa* and their entry is heralded by the beat of drums. They chant in chorus the *mahapīṭa* and benedictory refrains. One monk then conducts a short sermon outlining the meritorious deeds performed so far. He then 'gives' merit by

advising the devotees to share the merit with gods and all living creatures, and to aspire to attain *Nibbāna* in the dispensation of the future Buddha *Maitreya*, after having enjoyed human and celestial pleasures for a long time, and never having to suffer birth in a state of woe.

The ceremony ends with the distribution of *paritta* water and thread as before. Usually the ceremony is followed by a great almsgiving and the proceedings are the same as those described in connection with the all-night ceremony.

4. Gihī Piritā (Paritta recited by laymen)

Sometimes overnight *paritta* ceremonies are performed by laymen, almost in the same manner as monks do, with of course a few minor modifications. It is really a substitute for the traditional *tis pāyē piritā* chanted by monks, adapted for convenience and economic reasons. The *gihī pirit* is quite popular in remote rural areas where it is very difficult and expensive to provide transport and dwelling facilities for monks who have to be gathered from a number of temples scattered over an extensive area to suffice for an overnight *paritta* ceremony.

A *maṇḍapa* is erected in the same manner as for the orthodox ceremony, but an *indrakṛtā* is never constructed. The *maṇḍapa* may be artistically decorated, or simple and austere. Whatever the embellishments, it is important to have an enclosed area, demarcated at least by a white cloth, drawn like a parape. It is surmounted with a white canopy where the traditional ritual accessories are hung. Instead of chairs, cushions or pillows are arranged inside the *maṇḍapa*. They are covered with white sheets. The centre table is of an appropriate height. The casket of relics, the ola-leaf *Paritta* text and the *pirit huya* are replaced by a Buddha picture or statue, a printed *Paritta* text and a ball of white thread respectively. Drum music too is generally omitted, it may be employed if conveniently available. All other appurtenances such as the *pān kaḷaya*, *pun kalas*, *lada pas mal*, *pahan pāla* etc. are utilised.

In the villages there are men who are specially trained for reciting *pirit*. Young boys with a good clear voice are chosen for training if they show sufficient aptitude and interest. Almost every village has a leader among these reciters and it is he who does the *anusāsana* at the beginning of the ceremony, and the *anumodanā* at the end. Only elderly men participate in *paritta* ceremonies. As a rule women never take part. They are not even permitted to step inside the enclosure once it is set apart for the ceremony.

The reciters bathe and wear fresh clean white garments to ensure ritual purity. They have an early vegetarian dinner before the ceremony about 7.00 p.m. Fish or dry fish may be included in the dinner, but as a rule meat is not served. The more orthodox reciters prefer to forego the dinner altogether, as such abstention marks a closer approximation to monastic conduct.

Before entering the *maṇḍapa* they anoint themselves with lime juice as a further purificatory measure. After sitting down inside the *maṇḍapa*, the leader administers *pañca sīla* to the reciters and the devotees sitting around. Thereafter, the ceremony is conducted in the same manner as by monks.....the *maha pirit*, *yuga pirit* and *hamāra* are all recited similarly. The ceremony is concluded with the distribution of *paritta* water and thread. A morning meal is served to the reciters like an *upāsaka dāna* (i.e. alms offered to lay Buddhists who have observed the eight precepts), and it is followed by the traditional dedication of merit (*puññānumodanā*) and the noble aspiration (*patthanā*).

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